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ONEforest

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A Multi-Criteria Decision Support System For
A Common Forest Management to Strengthen Forest
Resilience, Harmonise Stakeholder Interests and
Ensure Sustainable Wood Flows

D7.1 MFA model and impact assessment through streamlined
LCA/S-LCA for each CSR

A Multi-Criteria Decision Support System for a Common Forest Management to Strengthen Forest Resilience, Harmonise Stakeholder Interests and Ensure Sustainable Wood Flows

Deliverable 7.1

Title: MFA model and impact assessment through streamlined LCA/S-LCA for each CSR

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Executive summary

This document is the Deliverable 7.1

This deliverable aims to provide the Material Flow Analysis (MFA) along the Forest Wood Value Chain (FWVC) and a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for each semi-finished product included in the FWVC in Europe as well as a streamlined social life cycle assessment (sLCA) for the different sectors. These methodologies were applied to four Case Study Regions (CSRs) in Europe, namely CSR 1, Estonia; CSR 2, Grisons in Switzerland; CSR 3, Catalonia in Spain; and CSR 4, Hesse and Thuringia in Germany. A general FWVC was identified among the CSRs and then, a MFA was done per each CSR, identifying the different wood industries producing the semi-finished products from wood removals of the forest as well as possible inaccuracies (e.g. over- or underestimation of production by statistical offices) in the data available for the FWVC in each CSR. At the same time, LCA provides the ecological impacts of the various processes within the FWVC per each semi-finished product of the FWVC in each CSR whereas the sLCA gives insights into social factors along the FWVC in the CSR. The results of the MFA, LCA and sLCA will provide a base for analysis and opportunities for the development of future scenarios for the Dynamic Value Chain Model (DVCM).

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Glossary

1,4-DB	1,4-dichlorobenzene
ADP	Abiotic depletion potential
ADPF	Abiotic depletion potential, fossil fuels
AP	Acidification potential
BES	Biodiversity and forest ecosystem services
BIO	Biodiversity
BEC	Bioeconomy
CFC	Chlorofluorocarbons
CFC-11	Chlorofluorocarbon-11
CH	Switzerland
C ₂ H ₄	Ethylene
CO	Carbon monoxide
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CSR	Case study region
DE	Germany
DVCM	Dynamic value chain model
EE	Estonia
EP	Eutrophication potential
EPF	European Panel Federation
eq	Equivalent
ES	Spain
EU	European Union
FAETP	Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity potential
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FES	Forest ecosystem services
FWVC	Forest wood value chain
GHG	Greenhouse gases emissions
GLO	Short name for global in Ecoinvent database
GWP	Global warming potential
HDF	High density fibreboard
HCFCs	Hydrochlorofluorocarbons
HTP	Human toxicity potential
HW	Hardwood
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LDF	Low density fibreboard
m ³ (f)	Wood fibre equivalent
m ³ (fob)	Wood fibre equivalent over bark
MAEP	Marine aquatic ecotoxicity potential

MDF	Medium density fibreboard
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
NMVOC	Non-methane volatile organic compounds
NH ₃	Ammonia
NO	Nitrogen oxide
NO _x	Nitrogen oxides
ODP	Ozone layer depletion potential
OSB	Oriented Strand Board
PMFP	Particulate matter formation potential
POP	Photochemical oxidation potential
RER	Short name for Europe in Ecoinvent database
RoW	Short name for rest of the world in Ecoinvent database
Sb	Antimony
SFM	Sustainable forest management
SO ₂	Sulphur dioxide
SO _x	Sulphur oxides
TETP	Terrestrial ecotoxicity potential
SW	Softwood
UNEP	United Nations Environmental Program
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UV	Ultraviolet
WDP	Water depletion potential
WP	Work package

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1 Introduction

Climate change and environmental degradation are threats to the world, mitigation actions are needed. The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) ultimate objective is “to achieve the stabilization of the greenhouse gases (GHG) concentration in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system” (United Nations, 1992). Mitigation of GHG emissions needs a combination of reducing the emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) as well as increasing the CO₂-storage (Machado et al., 2015). The new EU forest strategy (EC 2019) helps increasing the absorption of CO₂, forces to improve the resilience of forests, and promotes a circular economy encouraging biodiversity (European Union: European Commission, 2019). Additionally, the European Commission’s commitment through the European Green Deal’s strategy, targets to transform the EU through a bioeconomy by having net zero emissions of GHG by 2050, resource-efficient economic growth and a fair society (European Union: European Commission, 2019). Forests and wood-based products play a significant role in fighting against climate change and environmental degradation (Ellison et al., 2011) through CO₂-uptakes in the growth phase and carbon storage in the use phase.

Forest products are the main biomass sources not directly competing with food and feed in Europe. They can be used as raw materials for a diverse range of products including chemicals, with the possibility of substituting fossil-based products and the possibility to be recycled and reused in line with the circular bioeconomy (Hetemäki et al., 2017). Wood-based products gaining more attention from the public due to various reasons such as their diverse applications and ability to substitute products originating from fossil resources, or creating a high demand for woody biomass as a material and energy source (Gonçalves et al., 2021; Klein et al., 2015).

Forest management and forest biomass production are commonly studied separately from wood processing. The FWVC is rarely investigated entirely in both considering the continuous value chain from forest to wood-based products (Auer and Rauch, 2021b) and in the view of the three dimensions of sustainability (economic, ecologic, social) applied to the FWVC in the context of a circular bioeconomy (Toppinen et al., 2020). In a supposed future research agenda, Santos et al. (2019) pointed out to include the combination of optimization and sustainability assessment of traditional wood supply chains beside the biomass-to-bioenergy supply chain as these traditional wood supply chains are the main wood consumers worldwide.

A broad understanding of the forest wood value chain (FWVC) based on consistent data and knowledge how woody biomass is used is crucial to support a circular bioeconomy (Gonçalves et al., 2021). Low data consistency and highly heterogeneous data characterize the FWVC. Even though it is identified as significant factor determining the quality of the FWVC assessments (Bösch et al., 2015; Budzinski et al., 2017; Weimar, 2011). However, a detailed quantification of regional wood flows in general within one set of data is still missing but is seen as an essential basis for evaluating supply security, the economic and the ecological contribution (Bösch et al., 2015; Budzinski et al., 2017) of the hardwood-based sector to mitigate climate change.

The report aims to provide preliminary data sets on quantified wood flows and on the ecological impact of semi-finished wood products which serve as basis for a holistic and consequential evaluation of regional FWVC in the four CSRs. Thus, the report addresses the identified gaps by modelling and describing the FWVCs from forests to semi-finished product industries by the methods of MFA and LCA. The MFA provides a consistent quantified data set of wood flows from resource to production for each CSR. This was done by modelling MFA for each CSR, based on current wood utilization pathways (material and energy use) from fellings to semi-finished products complemented by imports and exports in and outside of the CSRs. The here

applied streamlined LCA assesses and quantifies the environmental impacts of the FWVC from forest processes to the production of semi-finished products (cradle-to-gate).

This report serves as the preliminary result of the work package (WP) 7. Herein obtained interim results will be used in the upcoming WP 7 tasks to model the Dynamic Value Chain Model (DVCM). Therefore, the results of the MFA, the LCA and the sLCA play an important role in ONEforest.

1.1 Case study regions

MFA and streamlined LCA were applied to model the downstream FWVCs and to quantify wood flows and environmental impacts of the semi-finished products of the FWVCs within the four case study regions (CSRs) of the ONEforest project. The CSRs were chosen to consider regional differences in climate and forest conditions, forest growth and various wood supply chains. The CSRs were chosen to consider regional differences in climate and forest conditions, forest growth and various wood supply chains. The CSRs were defined as: CSR 1, Estonia; CSR 2, Catalonia in Spain (ES); CSR 3, Grisons in Switzerland (CH); and CSR 4, Hessen and Thuringia in Germany (DE). Each CSR represents a specific type of forest in Europe, as well as, forest ownership, and wood industries available (see Table 1).

Table 1. Overview of case study regions.

	Estonia	Grisons (CH)	Catalonia (ES)	Hesse/Thuringia (DE)
Geography	Northern Europe	Central Europe	Southern Europe	Central Europe
Forest type	Boreal/Hemi-boreal forests	Alpine forests	Mediterranean forests	Continental forests
Total land CSR	4,533,900 ha	710,500 ha	281,000 ha	3,728,600 ha
Forest land	2,332,600 ha	201,240 ha	281,000 ha	1,443,300 ha
Managed forest land	2,003,800 ha	184,240 ha	187,000 ha*	1,356,700 ha*
Main species	Scots pine, Norway spruce, silver birch, alder and aspen	Spruce, larch and Scots pine	Scots pine and black pine	European beech, spruce and Scots pine
Forest ownership	Private and state	Private and state	Private and state	Private, corporate, and state
Wood-based industries	From sawmill to pulp and biorefinery	Only sawmill and energy production	Sawmill, poles and stake, veneer and plywood, wood energy products, and energy production	From sawmill to pulp and biorefinery

* partially protected

All CSRs have wood-based industries, however, Estonia and Hesse/Thuringia (DE) show a higher diversification in their wood-based industries compared to Grisons and Catalonia. In CSRs 1 and 4 following semi-finished products are produced: sawnwood, veneer and plywood sheets, wood-based panels, wood pulp, wood energy products, and wood-based energy (power and heat). Grisons (CH), CSR 2, is the region with the lowest share of processing industry since only sawmill and energy production (power and heat) is present. In CSR 3 Catalonia (ES) sawnwood, poles and stakes, wood energy products, and wood-based energy (power and heat) are produced.

1.2 Report outline

This report first introduces the theoretical framework for the applied methodologies, MFA and streamlined LCA and sLCA. This is followed by the method and material chapter, which includes the FWVC as basic structure for applying the methodologies. It includes methodological approach of the MFA and sLCA applied in each CSR, and how the streamlined LCA was applied to each industry in the FWVCs. At the end, MFA results are presented per CSR, followed by LCA results for the semi-finished products of the FWVC in each CSR. The modelling of the LCA is based on the wood value chains of the MFA in the CSRs. In terms of a streamlined LCA, the environmental impacts are assessed in the regional background system, while the process chains of the wood products are based on the main processes in Europe. At the end of the report, the different approaches and methodologies as well as the data quality is discussed and an outlook is given on how the MFA, LCA and sLCA results will be used in the DVCM.

2 Theoretical framework

2.1 Material flow analysis

MFA systematically documents material flows and stocks in a defined space and time (Cencic and Rechberger, 2008) and it provides means for reconciliation of highly heterogeneous data (Lenglet et al., 2017). Therefore, it is a promising tool to overcome heterogeneous, mismatching and missing data in order to investigate a wood value network.

MFA is a method to understand the “material basis of the economy” by describing, investigating and evaluating “the metabolism of anthropogenic and geogenic systems” (Brunner and Rechberger, 2016). Thus, a MFA systematically keeps records of material flows and connects sources and sinks through the material pathways (Cencic and Rechberger, 2008). MFA was developed to describe and analyse individual processes, e.g. in chemical production or waste management. Nowadays, it is often used to analyse large systems, such as national economies and can help identifying major changes in material flows, especially when they are comparable with each other. Therefore, MFA is recognized as a scientific tool to support decision makers, notably in the field of environmental policy (Brunner and Rechberger, 2016) and has become one of the most important methods in scientific fields (Brunner and Rechberger, 2016). Currently, MFA is applied in forest wood value chains (Auer and Rauch, 2021a; Babuka et al., 2020; Lenglet et al., 2017; Parobek et al., 2014; Schweinle et al., 2020) to provide consistent datasets of the FWVCs and to evaluate wood flows from resource to production.

To resolve data contradictions and to find the most appropriate values for the model, data reconciliation as a statistical adjustment of values is an important feature in MFA modelling (Brunner and Rechberger 2016). Accordingly, Lenglet et al. (2017) and (Auer and Rauch, 2021a) demonstrated the importance and usability of MFA to reconcile very heterogeneous databases. If the system of equation is over-determined and some of the given data is normally distributed, the least squares method can be applied to resolve data contradictions. The applied data reconciliation method applied in this work is based on Cencic (2016). To solve the model, data reconciliation alters the mean value of uncertain data, so that at least data contradictions disappear. If the sum of squares of all necessary data adoptions reaches a minimum (objective function), a solution is found (method of least squares). Furthermore, data uncertainties are resolved and, again assuming that uncertainties are normally distributed based on mean value and standard deviation, unknown values are calculated based on normally distributed independent random variables by the law of error propagation. To consider the uncertainty of heterogeneous data, standard uncertainty (uncertainty of the mean value) is used instead of the standard deviation that describes the deviation within the sample. The standard uncertainty is calculated based on a ten-year data sample, if available from 2009 up to 2018. If fewer values are given in a sample, a standard uncertainty of 10% is applied. Following this, the MFA was performed with the software STAN (TU Wien IWR, 2012).

MFA includes various indicators to evaluate the accuracy of the network model data. The indicator “degree of over-determination” shows the number of equations without unknown variables based on transforming the given equation system. The indicator “quality of data reconciliation” sets the minimum value to 0, meaning that data contradictions are not solvable due to gross errors within all mean values of variables, and the maximum value to 1, meaning that no adjustments regarding the mean values of the systems were necessary to obtain a fitting system (TU Wien IWR, 2012).

The software STAN (TU Wien IWR, 2012) provides the indicator “z-score”. It represents the number of standard deviations from the mean value of the input data in the MFA. The z-score provides information on the data quality and the measures, which the scope of data reconciliation needs to calculate one consistent dataset.

Herein, the FWVCs are described by wood flows and processes. The processes represent the forest sources of the four CSRs and their different wood consuming industries with semi-finished wood products or by-products as output flows. Additionally, processes are used to consolidate or distribute wood flows within the system. Such processes are called “auxiliary processes”. Input and output flows connect the various processes with each other and show thereby the wood flows through the FWVC. Although, STAN offers the integration of stocks, they were not applied in the MFA model. The law of mass conservation requires a balanced overall system and thus, balanced system processes. However, several studies claimed low data consistency and very heterogeneous data in the FWVC as major drawback in receiving high quality results. Cencic (2016) solved the problem of lacking data availability and mismatching data sources by using a data reconciliation algorithm that is implemented in the software STAN. The applicability of the reconciliation algorithm and the achievable data quality for the FWVC were investigated and confirmed by Auer and Rauch (2021a) exemplified on the hardwood value chain in Germany. Auer and Rauch (2021a) successfully provide one consistent data set on the basis of different statistical sources and thus often mismatching data. They also present not-recorded wood fellings and volumes of produced wood products, which are statistically not recorded. The applied MFA aims to provide one consistent dataset for each CSR as required as basis for the applications of methods such as LCA. Therefore, the algorithm was applied here, too. For further theoretical background of the algorithm, we here refer to Cencic (2016).

2.2 Streamlined life cycle assessment

LCA captures the environmental aspects and potential environmental impacts of a product throughout its life cycle, i.e. from raw material extraction through production, use and end-of-life treatment (reuse, recycling, energy recovery and disposal). For the environmental assessment of the FWVC, the approach of a streamlined LCA was applied. It was based on the methodology of a “full” LCA according to ISO 14040-14044, however, the approach was driven by simplifications. The standardized methodology of a “full” LCA comprises four mandatory phases (Frischknecht, 2020; ISO 14044, 2020; ISO 14040:2006/AMD 1:2020, 2020; Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014):

- **(1)** Within the first phase (**goal and scope**), the goal of LCA study indicates the application, the reason for conducting the study and its target group, while the scope of LCA study includes the description of the product (system) and the definition of the functional unit. It defines the quantifiable benefit of the product (system). In addition, the system boundary of the product system, assumptions, data requirements, allocation procedures, cut-off criteria and methodology of life cycle impact assessment as well as the impact categories are defined. Furthermore, any limitations of LCA study are identified.
- **(2)** Based on the scope of LCA study, the **life cycle inventory (LCI)** analysis deals with the qualitative, and even more the quantitative data collection of the processes within the system boundary of the product systems by assessing the input and output flows of the processes. For each process within the system boundary, energy, raw material, ancillary

inputs, product, co-products, waste, emissions into air, soil and water are quantified related to the functional unit.

- **(3) The life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)** uses the results of LCI analysis. The elementary flows of the product system are classified and characterized based on the applied LCIA assessment methodology. The result of LCIA is the assessment of the potential environmental impacts of the product system by means of impact category indicators.
- **(4) After LCIA, the final phase of LCA method involves an interpretation,** sensitivity and uncertainty analyses, and statements on data quality.

Since a streamlined LCA approach was chosen for the project, which assumes simplifications in LCI analysis phase, while phases 1 and 2 were applied analogously to a “full” LCA. The interpretation of the LCA results (phase 4) will be part of the further work under WP 7 and the modelling of the DVCM and are therefore not reported. Additional analyses and interpretations such as normalization, weighting and grouping are optional elements within a LCA study. None of these were applied in this project.

Since streamlined LCAs were first discussed in the 1990s, a number of simplified LCA studies have been conducted. However, there is no uniform definition of a streamlined or simplified LCA in the literature. Beemsterboer et al. (2020) identified five logics for simplifying LCAs. One of these logics is the so-called inventory data substitution, which can be divided into simplifications in terms of model structure, input flow and output flow. Streamlined LCAs that focus on the model structure distinguish between a foreground and a background system. While the foreground system is evaluated in detail, the background system is neglected as a black box (Beemsterboer et al., 2020).

Since the project needs to consider different CSRs and provides industry-wide information, the approach of a foreground and background system was adjusted. Based on the cradle-to-gate system boundary, a streamlined LCA approach was applied that distinguishes between a foreground system, an European-average background and a CSR-specific background system (Figure 1). In the foreground system, LCI was based on industry-wide manufacturing data of the product, while for the ancillary material, a background system was assumed that refers to average EU-LCI data. For example, European LCI data were considered when modelling ancillary materials such as glue. In the CSR-specific background system, relevant process steps of the CSR were modelled using national LCI data. For example, the country specific energy consumption mix, transportation processes connecting suppliers with consumers, or the production and harvesting of roundwood from sustainable forest management are modelled with regard to the CSRs.

System boundary: cradle-to-gate (semi-finished products) *

* not considered: maintenance of machinery, construction of buildings and roads
 ** cascade use is not considered as well as the allocation between several product life cycles → cut-off method
 *** differentiation between soft and hard wood in harvesting/storage and processes are needed in LCA?

Figure 1. Streamlined LCA approach with differentiated foreground and background systems.

This streamlined LCA approach was chosen, because the objective was to assess FWVCs and their contribution to environmental challenges, instead of only evaluating different manufacturing technologies of a product system or comparing the manufacturing of a product in different CSRs. However, the aim was to reveal the impacts of different energy grid mixes or transport distances so that they are mapped in a CSR-specific background system.

2.3 Streamlined social life cycle assessment

Sustainability is usually described by ecological, economic and social dimensions. Whereas the ecological factors can be assessed by the method of Life Cycle Analysis/Assessment (LCA) (e.g. ISO 14044) and the economic factors by the method of Life Cycle Costing (LCC) (e.g. ISO 15686-5), the social Life Cycle Assessment (sLCA) relies on guidelines and handbooks for various different methodologies, which describe how to conduct an sLCA.

Nevertheless the UNEP Guidelines are a document, which helps users to understand and conduct an sLCA (UNEP, 2020). First published in 2009, the sLCA follows the four steps of the LCA, which comprises of “setting the Goal and Scope of a study (Goal and Scope), collecting data (Inventory), assessing the risks and potential impacts (Impact Assessment) and interpreting results (Interpretation)” (ibid).

Together with the LCA and the LCC the sLCA provides an insight into the sustainability of products, services and organizations and is named Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment.

The project ONEforest focuses the sustainable forest management but also the use of forest and wood products. Therefore, the sLCA is an essential part of the methodological approach in showing how the working and living environment for people can be secured and improved.

3 Method and Material

3.1 Forest wood value chain

The system boundaries of the FWVCs were predetermined by the project's grant agreement. Wood flows from forest to industry as well as by-products and semi-finished product flows between industries are within the system boundaries. Thus, the system boundaries include the utilization pathways of wood from cradle-to-gate while differing between hardwood and softwood from forest to industry as well as by-products and semi-finished-product flows between industries. Considered products are sawnwood, veneer, wood panels, wood pulp, wood energy products as well as energy production for incineration processes based on wood, bark, sawmill by-products and post-consumer wood (if applicable). As a result, the model does not count third transformation industries such as the furniture industry or the building industry. The spatial boundaries are the national or federal state boundaries of the specific CSRs. Imports and exports in or outside the CSRs were considered, too. The conducted MFA focuses on the year 2018, since this was the latest year with fully available and proofed data mostly available in all four CSRs. The MFA does not show any connection to the previous or the following year.

3.2 Material Flow Analysis

3.2.1 Basic methodological approach

In the first step, input and (by-) product output figures were documented mainly using data provided by the country-specific Federal Statistical Offices (FSOs). Wood supply, processing, and consumption sectors were then described in relation to qualitative, quantitative, and technical parameters as the second step. The depth of processing technologies and products had to be streamlined in order to assess the overall system. The categorization of the FWVC into individual processes was based on raw materials, processing steps and products which, on the one hand, are as homogeneous (property-based) as possible, and on the other hand, are sufficiently differing from other processes. The aggregations are in line with other studies (Auer and Rauch, 2021a; Kalt and Kranzl, 2012; Lenglet et al., 2017; Parobek et al., 2014; Weimar, 2011). If no official or scientifically published data were available or not sufficiently reliable, other data sources (e.g., wood monitoring and consumption studies, reports of federations, etc.) were used to close data gaps. In cases of entirely missing data, the authors made their own calculations based on assumptions.

Based on the different utilization pathways in the FWVCs, a general MFA model (Figure 2) was defined. The model includes all industries and pathways that are present in one or more of the CSRs. If the industries or pathways were not applicable in the CSRs, the connecting flows in the model were defined with the value "zero" and STAN hides these flows automatically. Table 2 gives an overview on the industries present in the individual CSRs.

3.2.1 Units, data and conversion factors

The measuring systems of wood quality assortments and wood products vary highly. This results in a low direct comparability of mass flows. Different authors (Auer and Rauch, 2021a; Lenglet et al., 2017; Weimar, 2011) emphasized the importance of a fixed measurement system for modelling wood flows. Therefore, the wood fibre equivalent (m^3 (f)), introduced by Weimar (2011), is applied in the ONEforest project to investigate wood flows (i.e. their fibre content) from source to use. The wood fibre equivalent (m^3 (f)) describes the equivalent volumes of wood fibres or wood-based fibres in the fibre-saturated state which a product contains (Bösch et al., 2015). Usually, the wood fibre equivalent does not consider the bark, however, based on Auer and Rauch (2021a) this study applied the unit of wood fibre equivalent over bark (m^3 (fob)). The conversion factors that were applied in the calculations were based on Weimar (2011), Lenglet et al. (2017) and own calculations (Table 3).

Table 3. Conversion factors applied in the MFA.

product	unit	conversion factor for m^3 (f)	source
round wood	m^3	1	Weimar (2011)
roundwood (imported or exported) softwood	t	1.05 (greenwood density)	own calculation
roundwood (imported or exported) hardwood	t	1.12 (greenwood density)	own calculation
wood fuel	m^3	1	Weimar (2011)
fuelwood	t	1.02	own calculation
fuelwood softwood	t	1.13	own calculation
fuelwood hardwood	t	0.87	own calculation
firewood softwood (green weight)	t	1.13	own calculation
firewood hardwood (green weight)	t	0.98	own calculation
garden wood	m^3	1	Weimar (2011)
landscape care wood	m^3	1	Weimar (2011)
by-products / processing residues	m^3	1	Weimar (2011)
sawmill residues	t	1.1	Lenglet et al. (2017)
softwood by-products / processing residues	t air dry	1.98	Weimar (2011)
hardwood by-products / processing residues	t air dry	1.42	Weimar (2011)
post-consumer wood	t air dry	1.82	Weimar (2011)
forest wood chips	m^3	1	Lenglet et al. (2017)
forest wood chips (bulk density)	t	2.54	own calculation
sawmill woodchips	t	1.1	Lenglet et al. (2017)
sawnwood	m^3	1	Weimar (2011)
veneer sheets	m^3	1	Weimar (2011)
plywood	m^3	0.96	Weimar (2011)
particleboard (incl. OSB)	m^3	1.25	Weimar (2011)
MDF	m^3	1.39	Lenglet et al. (2017)
fibre boards	m^3	1.47	Weimar (2011)
mechanical pulp	t	2.22	Weimar (2011)
chemical pulp	t	2.13	Weimar (2011)
wood pellets	t	2.22	Weimar (2011)
wood briquettes	t	2.22	Weimar (2011)
charcoal	t	1.65	Weimar (2011)
post-consumer wood	t bone dry	2.163	own calculation
landscape care wood	t bone dry	1.980	own calculation
residual wood	t bone dry	1.923	own calculation
fuelwood	t bone dry	2.34	own calculation
sawmill woodchips	t bone dry	2.5	own calculation
softwood (calculation based on spruce)	t bone dry	2.6	own calculation
hardwood (calculation based on beech)	t bone dry	1.8	own calculation

Additionally, 1 MWh was assumed to equal 3.6 GJ and 1 t bone dry equals 18.67 GJ (Gößwein et al., 2018).

The assortment and product classification is based on FAO (2022a), whereas by-products cover industrial residues such as wood chips, particles and wood for agglomerates. Pulpwood covers, the assortment “pulpwood, round and split”.

The authors here refer to D6.4 which provides the starting data base for the MFA of each CSR and lists the considered product codes. Thereupon, the conversion factors were applied to unify the different units.

3.2.2 General assumptions

Some products are only recorded on an aggregated level, such as by-products, import and export volumes of roundwood/fuelwood. Thus, a differentiation between softwood and hardwood based on statistical data is not possible. If no information on soft-/hardwood shares were available, following assumptions were made: (1) By-products are distributed to softwood and hardwood according the share of produced sawnwood. (2) Import/export volumes of roundwood or fuelwood are distributed according the share of the specific wood assortment removed within the CSR.

Imports into the CSRs and exports out of the CSRs were considered in case specific data were available. In the CSRs 3 and 4, only trade data from/to the CSRs from/to other countries was available, but not from/to the other federal states within the same country. Thus, in CSRs 3 and 4 import and export values were calculated within the MFA and can be biased. Imports and exports are fixed to the spatial boundaries of the CSRs, i.e. if companies are located near the border within the CSR, it was assumed that they use only resources supplied within the CSR. Vice versa, if a company is located nearby outside the CSR, it was assumed that the companies are not considered within the CSR-specific MFA. However, it is possible that exports are allocated to that company.

In CSRs 1 and 3, it was present the production of poles and stakes. The poles refers to wood poles for overhead lines and stakes refer to piles, pickets and stakes of wood, pointed but not sawn lengthwise. The assortment used to produce them is sawlogs and veneer logs.

If no country-specific processing yields were found, the country-specific information of FAO et al. (2020) were applied: the Spanish values were taken for the Catalan MFA and the European average values were used for the Estonian MFA.

Usually, wood removals are recorded under bark. Therefore, the bark share was added in CSR 2 and CSR 4 according the assumptions an average bark share of 12.8% for softwood (spruce 11.1%, pine 16.9%) and 6.4% for hardwood (beech 4.7%, oak 21.6%). CSR 1 and CSR 3 report fellings in m³ over bark.

Table 3 lists the conversion that were applied to unify the units of product data which was originally provide in different units. For example, the official unit of roundwood in m³ under bark equals the unit wood fibre equivalent, thus 1 m³ under bark corresponds to 1 m³ (f).

3.2.3 CSR 1 Estonia

As stated in the D6.4, the following different sources provide felling statistics for Estonia.

The **FAO Forestry Production and Trade statistics** provides data which include fellings in state-owned and private-owned forests, however it does not distinguish between type of ownership in the reported data sets. The FAO data set provides information on the type of removed wood assortment (i.e. sawlog/veneer logs, pulpwood and fuelwood) and the removed wood species (i.e. softwood and hardwood) (FAO, 2022b).

The **State Forest Management Centre (RMK)** offers data about state-owned forest products in relation to sales figures that partly do not distinguish between softwood and hardwood. Fuelwood assortments are not separately recorded by hardwood and softwood. However, the wood removals of private-owned forests are not included in these data sets.

The **RMK Annual Reports of 2010 and 2015** provide data of sold forest material/sawnwood (m³) separated by the wood assortments logs, pulpwood, firewood and wood chips (including cutting residues). However, the Annual reports do not present the data separated in hardwood and softwood and only removals of state-owned forests are listed.

The aim of the wood flow analysis based on the MFA method is to visualize the wood flows through the CSR specific FWVC and to provide a complete picture as far as possible. Separated information on wood assortment and wood species is more important to reach the goal than the differentiation between the types of ownership. Consequently, the FAO data set was chosen as forestry data basis for the Estonian wood flow analysis.

Statistics Estonia offers a database in which production data could be gathered for the relevant years 2009-2018 per online queries. The products were searched in the database "TO68 - TO77: Manufacturing production by list of manufacturing products (TTL)" (Statistics Estonia, 2022b) by using the 6 first digits of the 8 digit International Code of PRODCOM. The data are visualized in a web browser and can be downloaded as CSV text file for every year separately. Additionally, Statistics Estonia offers statistics on energy production and consumption which is reported in KE023: ENERGY BALANCE SHEET by indicator, type of fuel/energy and year (Statistics Estonia, 2022a). Trade information on import and export volumes of different wood assortments or products are gathered through the EUROSTAT database (Eurostat, 2022).

In Estonia, besides particleboards and OSB-panels, all fibreboards (only excluding MDF) are recorded as fibreboards within a subordinated category. Thus, the MFA displays only this aggregated category since the share of the different fibreboards were unknown. Based on the stated density, which is lower than 0.5 g/cm³, the input share of 95% softwood by-products and 5% hardwood by-products was applied following the FAO et al. (2020). Production data of particleboard was collected through the Statistics Estonia (Statistics Estonia, 2022b) and data of other fibreboards were collected through FAO Statistics (FAO, 2022b) since the latter provides the values in the required unit of m³.

In the reference year 2018, Estonia did not have a huge pulp industry. There was one plant that produced pulp from aspen recorded as thermomechanical wood pulp, t 90% k/a. Since this data is missing in the D6.4, it was added for the D7.1.

In 2020, the first test in a wood-based biorefinery was performed. The trial phase of wood-based biorefinery will end 2022. Thus, products should be on the market by the end of 2022. This means that for the use case of 2018 it is neglectable.

3.2.4 CSR 2 Grisons

The Swiss Forestry Statistics (FSO) (FSO, 2021) offers yearly data on removed wood assortments for softwood and hardwood differed by Canton and by private-owned and state-owned forests. The wood removals are recorded in m³ under bark. The bark was added according the general assumptions.

In Switzerland, the roundwood cutting reported by Canton is recorded in a five-year interval. Thus, for the CSR 1 Grisons sawmill industry data were available for the years 2007, 2012 and 2017 (FSO, 2018). Energy production based on wood is recorded in the “Wood Energy Statistics” divided by Canton and firing type. Additionally, conversion factors and softwood/hardwood shares in the energy-related wood assortments (Table 4) were provided and applied for Switzerland in general (Stettler, 2019).

Table 4. Assortment shares applied to energy production in Grisons.

Assortment	Assortment share in the total Swiss wood energy production	Share of hardwood
Fuelwood	34%	50% (own assumption, based on firelogs)
Firelogs unspecified	25%	50%
Residues	17%	30%
Wood pellets	11%	(raw material) 30%
Post-consumer wood	14%	-
Without specific information	-	40%

In the reference years 2018, two combined heat and power plants which using wood were located in Grisons. Together they supplied 49'1873.73 MWh in 2020. They used 184'233 m³ fuelwood whereof 54.4% were supplied from sources within Grisons and 44.7% were supplied from other Swiss Cantons, and 0.9% were imported from other countries (Bartlome and Vlaskou Badra, 2021). Since the yearly production and so, the yearly consumption is relatively constant, for the year 2018 the same production volumes and wood shares are applied to the power production in Grisons.

Trade data for sawlogs and pulpwood were gathered by personal interviews conducted by the Swiss Wood Innovation Network (S-WIN) (S-WIN, 2022) who supported the data collection in Grisons. Import volumes of sawlogs and fuelwood were derived from the Wood Flow Analysis of Grisons (Bartlome and Vlaskou Badra, 2021).

3.2.5 CSR 3 Catalonia

The Statistical Institute of Catalonia (Idescat) (Idescat, 2019) offers yearly data about removed wood assortments for softwood and hardwood by private-owned and state-owned forests. The wood removals are recorded in m³ over bark with the difference of firewood which is recorded in t fresh.

In Catalonia, the industrial roundwood is reported by ownership, state-owned (Generalitat de Catalunya and Local entities) as well as private-owned (private property), and separated by softwood and hardwood. Data was available from 1999 to 2019. To get the data on the assortment of sawlogs and veneer logs, pulpwood and fuelwood, the share of assortments of wood harvested provided by the project partner CTFC was used (see Table 5) (Raddi, 2021).

Table 5. Assortment shares applied to wood harvested in Catalonia.

Assortment	Assortment share for 2018
Sawlogs/veneer logs	45.2%
Pulpwood	7.5%
Fuelwood (forest wood chips)	15.2%
Fuelwood (firewood)	23.0%
Poles and stakes	9.1%

The share of fuelwood (forest wood chips) was used to estimate unrecorded fuelwood volumes because the forest wood chips were not reported by Idescat (2019).

Idescat offers a database in which production data could be gathered from 2006 to 2019 (Idescat, 2021). The source of the data is from the industrial Product Survey of the National Statistics Institute of Spain. The products were searched using the 8-digit International Code of PRODCOM.

For the energy industry, apparent consumption and total demand for forest biofuels in Catalonia was collected from the Forest Observatory of Catalonia (OFC) (OFC, 2021). The available data correspond to wood chips, pellets and firewood.

Furthermore, Idescat offers data regarding foreign trade information on import and export volumes of different wood assortments or products (Idescat, 2022). Data were gathered from 1994 to 2022, however, data for year 2022 are only added until the last month loaded (March 2022). The source of data is the Department of Customs and Excise of the State Tax Administrator Agency of Spain. The wood assortments and products were searched using the Customs Tariff Number, TARIC product with 6 digits.

Catalonia does not have veneer and plywood nor wood panel production. The volumes reported by Idescat (2021) correspond to second transformations, that means, veneer and plywood, and wood panels are imported and then finished in Catalonia. There is also no pulp and biorefinery industry in Catalonia, pulpwood for wood pulp production is exported to France and other Spanish states. The paper companies located in Catalonia do not produce pulp, they process paper and cardboards to produce packaging or paper with different finishes like coated paper. For the wood energy product industry, there was only production of pellets in Catalonia.

3.2.6 CSR 4 Hesse and Thuringia

Hesse and Thuringia are federal states of Germany. The Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture provides yearly “Wood Market Reports” (BMEL, 2022). Therein, wood fellings and removals are listed by federal state, type of ownership, wood assortment, and wood species groups (BMEL, 2022). Three types of ownerships are distinguished in Germany: state-owned, private-owned and others, whereas the latter one includes forests owned by the churches or – to a minor extent- foundations. The wood removals are recorded in m³ under bark. Thus, the share of bark was added as explained in the “General assumptions” section. However, the shares in Germany differed slightly from the other CSRs due to the higher share of hardwoods and the different share of wood species in one wood species group. Finally, for softwood 11.7% and for hardwood 6.7% were applied as conversion factors.

The amount of the annual sawnwood harvest as published in federal statistical reports does not consider all wood removals, since private forest owners (48% of all forests) are not obligated to report harvests to the statistical office (Jochem et al., 2015). Jochem et al. (2015)

calculated a share of 54% of the totally harvested wood as unrecorded in 2013, of which most of it was used as fuelwood. To address these challenges, wood flows which maybe unrecorded or come from an unknown source were included as separate input into the MFA model.

On a national level, the German Federal Statistical Office offers the “productions statics” (DESTATIS, 2022; StBA, 2016b, 2015b, 2014b, 2013b, 2012b, 2011b) and the “working paper of raw wood and semi-finished wood products” (StBA, 2019, 2017, 2016a, 2015a, 2014a, 2013a, 2012a, 2011a, 2010) which list the production and sales of wood products. Since these statistics are not fully broken down on a federal state level, a query was placed, as so-called official special evaluation to the General Information Service (AKD/LfStat). It is based on a request of index of goods (Güterverzeichnis für Produktionsstatistiken 2009/2019) which is comparable with the European PRODCOM Codes. Finally, the AKD delivered production volumes, trade data (Hesse/Thuringia – other countries), and wood-based energy produced in Hesse.

However, some of the production volumes could not be provided due to confidentiality issues. Therefore, an additional internet research was conducted using, e.g. the Bisnode database (company description based on NACE code) (Bisnode, 2022) and companies` websites, to complete the CSR 4 production volumes. The gathered data were crosschecked with the wood monitoring reports of the sawmill industry (Döring et al., 2020a), the wood panel industry (Döring et al., 2021a), the pulp and paper industry (Giesecking et al., 2021) and the veneer (Giesecking and Mantau, 2020) and plywood industry (Giesecking et al., 2020) which are offered two times in a decade and base on company surveys.

Information on energy production based on wood was not available for Thuringia. Therefore, assumptions were made based on the results of the Information Systems for Resources (INFRO) reports (Döring et al., 2021b, 2021c; Döring et al., 2020b). However, the reports represent the whole of Germany and not the single federal states of Hesse or Thuringia. Therefore, the modelled and simulated energy production of Hesse and Thuringia has a low reliability due to missing and highly aggregated input wood flows.

Volumes on trade between the CSR and other federal states are not available since they were not gathered by the statistics in Germany. Whenever data on trades were required to run the MFA, assumptions were made, or if applicable results were calculated by STAN (TU Wien IWR, 2012).

Type of processed assortments to produce a product and also the share of the input flows in one product production relied on the information of the wood monitoring reports: the sawmill industry (Döring et al., 2020a), the wood panel industry (Döring et al., 2021a), the pulp and paper industry (Giesecking et al., 2021) and the veneer (Giesecking and Mantau, 2020) and plywood industry (Giesecking et al., 2020). Exceptionally, pellets were not covered within these reports. Here, information of the German pellet association (DEPV, 2019) were used.

The official production statistics underestimates the sawnwood production volumes (Zimmermann et al., 2018). Accordingly, the latest study of Zimmermann et al. (2018) showed an underestimation of roundwood of about 13% within the sawnwood production compared to the official production statistics. This discrepancy mainly resulted from incomplete reporting by companies that were above the threshold and errors made whilst filling in the surveys. Sawmills under the company size threshold were not included, thus the total underestimation is likely to be even greater, approx. 50%. The MFA model of CSR 4 considers this aspect by

using the processing yields of the sawmill industry in connection with the self-investigated sawnwood production instead of using statistical data.

3.3 Streamlined life cycle assessment

This chapter presents the streamlined LCA applied to calculate the environmental impacts of the semi-finished products included in the FWVC per CSR. Following the theoretical framework explained in the section “2.2 Streamlined life cycle assessment” the following section describes the methods applied. First, the definition of goal and scope is presented, then the LCI is described with general assumptions per each industry included in the FWVC. In each industry a regional background system specific per CSR, a global background system using European average values and a foreground system were applied following the streamlined approach (see Figure 1). Finally, LCA results are presented in the section “4.2 LCA”. The interpretation and discussion of results will be included in upcoming scientific publications and further work under WP 7.

3.3.1 Definition of goal and scope

Following the standard DIN EN ISO 14044:2006 (ISO 14044, 2020), Table 6 summarize the goal and scope of LCA presented in this report.

Table 6. LCA Goal and scope definition.

Goal	To provide an environmental impact assessment of the FWVCs, assessing the ecological effects from the forest production to the production of semi-finished products
Product systems	Sawmilling softwood
	Sawmilling hardwood
	Poles and stakes softwood
	Poles and stakes hardwood
	Veneer and plywood softwood
	Veneer and plywood hardwood
	Particle board
	OSB
	MDF, HDF, LDF and other fibreboards
	Pulp production (kraft or sulphate process)
	Thermo mechanical pulp process
	Pellets production
	Briquettes production
Charcoal production	
Functional unit	Depending on the production system (1 m ³ , or 1 kg)
System boundary	From cradle to gate
	Utilization and disposal end-of-life, out of system boundaries
Cut-off criteria	Threshold of 1 mass-% of process, in a sum the cut-off flows must be below, < 5 mass-% of the entire process chain (in line with ISO 14040/44)
Allocation rules	Allocation between several product life cycles was not considered (see section 3.3.2 Life cycle inventory analysis)
LCIA methodology	CML-IA base line and ei – ReCiPe Midpoint (H) for specific environmental impacts (see section 3.3.3 Life cycle impact assessment)
Environmental impact categories included	Abiotic depletion potential (ADP)
	Abiotic depletion potential, fossil fuels (ADPF)
	Acidification potential (AP)
	Eutrophication potential (EP)
	Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity potential (FAETP)
	Global warming potential (GWP)

	Human toxicity potential (HTP)
	Marine aquatic ecotoxicity potential (MAEP)
	Ozone layer depletion potential (ODP)
	Photochemical oxidation potential (POP)
	Terrestrial ecotoxicity potential (TETP)
	Particulate matter formation potential (PMFP)
	Agriculture land occupation potential (ALOP)
	Water depletion potential (WDP)
General assumptions	Excluded maintenance of machinery, construction of buildings and roads
	Cascade of wood is not considered
	Distance and type of transportation followed the assumptions explained in the following subsections (see subsections Assumption average transport distances in each CSR and Assumption on transport data set)
Type and sources of data	Database Ecoinvent v3.8
	Literature (see sources in Table 9 to Table 20)

Assumed average transport distances in each CSR

The applied average transport distances in each CSR were calculated by using 50% of the radius of the whole span of the CSRs. Furthermore, the density per specific tree species was considered according to Pro:Holz Austria (2022) and calculated with 60% water content for fresh green biomass. Regarding these values, Table 7 shows the ton-kilometre per functional unit per CSR and tree species.

Table 7. Ton-kilometre per functional unit m³(f) per CSR and tree species.

Tree species	density with 60% water content (kg/m ³)	CSR 1	CSR 2	CSR 3	CSR 4
		ton-kilometre [t-km/m ³ (f)]			
Spruce	656	53	23	47	56
Pine	880	71	31	62	75
Larch	992	80	35	70	85
Fir	656	53	23	47	56
Beech	1,088	88	39	77	93
Birch	1,024	82	36	73	88
Acer	992	80	35	70	85
Ash	1,072	86	38	76	92
Oak	1,072	86	38	76	92

Assumed forestry production and harvesting of wood in each CSR

The production and harvesting of wood were modelled for all CSR. This was done by using the predetermined processes available in the Ecoinvent database v3.8. The processes are “market for sawlog and veneer log” and “market for pulpwood, market for forest wood chips”. All the processes were modelled separately for softwood and hardwood. These predetermined processes include the seeding, growing, harvesting and transportation processes in the forest. The processes are based on sustainable forest management, as the prevailing management practices in Europe without in Switzerland.

Assumed transport data set in each CSR

In all CSRs, transport was modelled as market average of lorries in Europe. However, the distances were adjusted to each CSR (Table 7).

3.3.2 Life cycle inventory analysis

The open source life cycle and sustainability assessment software openLCA 1.11.0 (GreenDelta, 2022) was used to conduct LCA. The software enables to combine two or more databases, this allows to combine unit and system processes for cut-off method, in one database. Most of the required data for LCI were retrieved from Ecoinvent database version 3.8 (Wernet et al., 2016). The Ecoinvent database version 3.8 offers three types of data packs with different methods applied: (1) allocation at the point of substitution, (2) consequential, and (3) cut off. The data pack selected as LCI in this report was “cut-off”.

Besides Ecoinvent databases, other literature was also used to enrich existing Ecoinvent datasets or to model process chains when LCI data were not available. The LCI data are described in detail in the different product systems.

Table 8 lists the wood industries and the specific processes that are present in each CSR. The identification of CSR-specific industries was based on the MFA results.

Table 8. Identification of relevant industries by CSR (✓ = applicable, - = not present).

Industry	Processes	CSR1	CSR2	CSR3	CSR4
Sawmilling softwood	Storing				
	Measurement				
	Debarking				
	Sorting				
	Primary cutting				
	Secondary cutting	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Sorting sawnwood				
	Drying				
	Edge trimming				
	Sorting side products				
	Collecting by-products				
	Chipping by-products				
	Sawmilling hardwood	Storing (opt. rained storing)			
Measurement					
Debarking					
Sorting					
Primary cutting					
Secondary cutting		✓	✓	✓	✓
Sorting sawnwood					
Drying					
Edge trimming					
Sorting side products					
Collecting by-products					
Chipping by-products					
Poles and stakes softwood		Debarking			
	Open air drying	✓	-	✓	-
	Dressing				
	Sorting				
	Treatment (with preservatives)				
Poles and stakes hardwood	Debarking				
	Open air drying				
	Dressing	-	-	✓	-
	Sorting				
	Treatment (with preservatives)				
Veneer and plywood	Debarking and cutting to length	✓	-	-	-
	Log preparation (soaking)				
	Peeling and clipping				

production softwood	Drying and sorting				
	Laying up, gluing, pressing, stacking				
	Trimming, sawing, storage				
Veneer and plywood production hardwood	Debarking and cutting to length				
	Log preparation (soaking)				
	Peeling and clipping	✓	-	-	✓
	Drying and sorting				
	Laying up, gluing, pressing, stacking				
	Trimming, sawing, storage				
<i>Wood-based panel industry</i>					
Particle board production	Chipping				
	Drying				
	Sorting				
	Blending				
	Forming	✓	-	-	✓
	Pre-pressing				
	Hot pressing				
	Cooling				
	Sanding				
		Trimming			
OSB production	Debarking				
	Chipping				
	Drying				
	Sorting				
	Blending	✓	-	-	-
	Forming				
	Pre-pressing				
	Hot pressing				
	Trimming and cutting				
MDF, HDF, LDF, and other fibreboards production	Debarking				
	Chipping including washing				
	Defibration				
	Drying and blending				
	Fleece formation	✓	-	-	✓
	Pressing (pre-press and hot press)				
	Trimming and cutting				
	Cooling and sanding				
	Sawing (cut to size)				
<i>Pulp and biorefinery industry</i>					
Pulp production (kraft or sulphate process)	Debarking and chipping				
	Cooking				
	Screening and washing				
	Oxygen delignification	✓	-	-	✓
	Bleaching				
	Post screening				
	Drying				
Thermo mechanical pulp process	Debarking				
	Chipping and washing				
	Dewatering				
	Pre-steaming and pre-heating	✓	-	-	-
	Recovery cycle				
	Grinding/refining				
	Screening and washing				
	TMP thickener				
<i>Wood energy product industry</i>					
Pellet production	Chipping				
	Milling				
	Conditioning	✓	-	✓	✓
	Pellet production process				
	Cooling				
	Handling and internal transportation				
Briquette production	Chipping				
	Screening	✓	-	-	-
	Milling				
	Conditioning				

	Densification (briquetting)				
	Cooling				
	Handling and internal transportation				
Charcoal production	Natural drying	✓	-	-	-
	Debarking				
	Cutting to length				
	Charcoal production in kiln				
	Crushing				
	Sieving and sorting				
	Handling of by-products				
	Handling and internal transportation				

Additionally, other sources from literature were used to adapt the Ecoinvent database v3.8 to the specific production conditions identified in the MFA results (see sources in

Table 9 to Table 20 in the following sections).

3.3.2.1 Sawmill industry

Sawmilling Softwood

In all CSRs, softwood sawnwood is produced (Table 8). Within the LCI, it was assumed that the technology and the share of processed softwood species is the same in each CSR. According to the regional background system, the processes of transportation, fuel production and electricity production were adapted to regional characteristics of the CSRs. If applicable, within the global background system data sets presenting the European average (RER) were used, otherwise global data sets (GLO) were used (see Figure A. 2 in Appendix A).

Specifics of the sawnwood softwood and its life cycle

The predefined dataset of Ecoinvent v3.8 provides data for general sawnwood products. It combines three specific products as inputs: boards, beams and laths. The process chain in a sawmill interlinks several processes, however, the process structure depends on the individual design and technologies in place for each sawmill. The sawing process starts with the sorting of the log at the sawmill. This activity ends with sawn softwood, at sawmill processes which are attributed directly to one of the by-products; dust emissions to the environment were not considered in general due to lack of data. The wood chips used in the heat production to feed the drying process were considered to be supplied internally which were generated from slabs and sidings when sawing. The characteristics of the of wood chips were: dry wood density 440 kg/m³; lower heating value 3007 MJ/m³, humidity was estimated approximately 50%. The considered air emission factors and the boiler efficiency represented average annual operations including start and stop (warm-up and shutdown). The boiler used was considered to be 300 kW and emission profile referred to the facility. A shrinkage ratio of between the moisture content of $u=30\% - 0\%$ was considered as 0.004 %/%. The dataset includes kiln drying of wet wood assumed as $u=60\%$ down to $u=10\%$, and shrinkage. The dataset did not include air emissions released from the wood, as the emissions were assumed to be comparable to emissions from natural drying during decomposition/rotting (Wernet et al., 2016). Drinking and surface water was added as elementary flow without a CSR-specific information to the process based on Rüter and Diedrichs (2012). The water was not used in a circuit process.

Table 9 shows the LCI of the production of 1 m³ kiln-dried softwood sawnwood.

Table 9. LCI of the production of 1 m³ kiln-dried softwood sawnwood.

Flow	Source
INPUT	
Wood resources	
Sawlogs and veneer logs softwood	Ecoinvent (based on softwood forestry, spruce/pine, sustainable forest management sawlog and veneer log, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S – DE/SE)
Transportation	Ecoinvent (based on market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cutoff, U - RER) and own assumption on average transport distances (Table 7)
Electricity, medium voltage	Ecoinvent (based on market for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, S – EE/CH/DE)
Fuels	
Industrial by-products own production	Ecoinvent (based wood chips production, softwood, at sawmill wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Operating resources	
Surface water	
Drinking water	Rüter and Diedrichs (2012)
Diesel	Ecoinvent (based on market for diesel, burned in building machine diesel, burned in building machine Cutoff, S - GLO)
Lubricating oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for lubricating oil lubricating oil Cutoff, S - RER)

Flow	Source
Sawnwood, softwood, raw, dried (u=10%)	1 m ³
Wood ash mixture, pure	Ecoinvent (based on market for wood ash mixture, pure wood ash mixture, pure Cutoff, U - Europe without Switzerland)
Waste mineral oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for waste mineral oil waste mineral oil Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Waste water	Rüter and Diedrichs (2012)
Emissions to air, soil and water	Elementary flows

Sawmilling Hardwood

In all CSRs hardwood sawnwood is produced (see Table 8). Within the LCI, it was assumed that the technology and the share of processed hardwood species is the same in all CSRs. According to the regional background system, the processes of transportation, fuel production and electricity production were adapted to regional characteristics of the CSRs. If applicable, within the global background system data sets presenting the European average were used, otherwise global data sets were used (Figure A. 2 in Appendix A).

Specifics of the sawnwood hardwood and its life cycle

The predefined dataset of Ecoinvent v3.8 provides data for general sawnwood products. It combines three specific products as inputs: boards, beams and laths. The process chain in a sawmill interlinks several processes; the process structure depends on the individual design and technologies in place for each sawmill. The sawing process starts with the sorting of the log at the sawmill. This activity ends with sawn hardwood, at sawmill processes which are attributed directly to one of the by-products; dust emissions to the environment were not considered due to lack of data. The wood chips used in the heat production to feed the drying process were considered to be supplied internally which were generated from slabs and sidings when sawing. The characteristics of the of wood chips were: dry wood density: 640 kg/m³; the low heating value: 4,208 MJ/m³, humidity was estimated approx. 50%. The considered air emission factors and the boiler efficiency represent average annual operation including start and stop (warm-up and shutdown). The boiler used was considered to be 300 kW and emission profile referred to the facility. A shrinkage ratio of between the moisture

content of $u=30\% - 0\%$ was considered as $0.004 \%/%$. The dataset includes kiln drying of wet wood assumed as $u=50\%$ down to $u=10\%$, and shrinkage. The dataset did not include air emissions released from the wood, as the emissions were assumed to be comparable to emissions from natural drying during decomposition/rotting (Wernet et al., 2016).

Drinking and surface water was added as elementary flow without a CSR-specific information to the process based on Rüter and Diedrichs (2012). It was assumed that 80% of the water was used in a circuit process. Table 10 shows the LCI of the production of 1 m^3 kiln-dried hardwood sawnwood.

Table 10. LCI of the production of 1 m^3 kiln-dried hardwood sawnwood.

Flow	Source
INPUT	
Wood resources	
Sawlogs and veneer logs hardwood	Ecoinvent (based on hardwood forestry, birch, sustainable forest management sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S - SE, hardwood forestry, beech, sustainable forest management sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S - DE, and hardwood forestry, oak, sustainable forest management sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S - DE)
Transportation	Ecoinvent (based on market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cutoff, U - RER) and own assumption on average transport distances (Table 7)
Electricity, medium voltage	Ecoinvent (based on country-specific market for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, S - EE/CH/ES/DE)
Fuels	
Industrial by-products own production	Ecoinvent (based on wood chips production, hardwood, at sawmill wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Operating resources	
Surface water	Rüter and Diedrichs (2012)
Drinking water	Rüter and Diedrichs (2012)
Diesel	Ecoinvent (based on market for diesel, burned in building machine diesel, burned in building machine Cutoff, S - GLO)
Lubricating oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for lubricating oil lubricating oil Cutoff, S - RER)

Flow	Source
OUTPUT	
sawnwood, hardwood, raw, dried ($u=10\%$)	1 m^3
Wood ash mixture, pure	Ecoinvent (based on market for wood ash mixture, pure wood ash mixture, pure Cutoff, U - Europe without Switzerland)
Waste mineral oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for waste mineral oil waste mineral oil Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Waste water	Assumption: 80% circuit use
Emissions to air, soil and water	Elementary flows

3.3.2.2 Veneer and plywood industry

Veneer and plywood softwood/hardwood

According to the MFA results, CSR 1 (Estonia) is the only region that produce veneer and plywood from softwood, while CSR 1 and CSR 4 (Hesse and Thuringia) are the only regions that produce veneer and plywood from hardwood (Table 8). Within the LCI, it was assumed that the technology and the share of processed softwood and hardwood species among CSRs is the same. According to the regional background system, the processes of transportation and electricity production were adapted to regional characteristics of the CSRs. If applicable,

within the global background system data sets presenting the European average without Switzerland were used, otherwise global data sets were used (see Figure A. 3 in Appendix A).

Specifics of the veneer and plywood softwood/hardwood and its life cycle

The predefined dataset of Ecoinvent v3.8 provides a general plywood production in Europe. It was not a specific plywood product in terms of a specific number and height of wood layers. The data was based on a sample of plywood production in Germany. Plywood is made of glued veneer sheets, which are thin sheets of wood obtained by sawing, cutting, or peeling. Veneers are produced using peeling and cutting machines. The coated veneers are stacked either manually or by machine. Usually, the coated veneers stacks are pre-compressed in an unheated one-daylight press. The next steps are hot pressing, where temperature is between 80 – 140 °C, time is between 14 – 90 minutes and pressure is between 0.6 – 2.5 N/mm². These conditions depend on the type of wood, the strength of the plywood and the type of adhesive. After gluing, veneer plywood is sanded, cut to standard or ordered measurements and graded according to quality. The most common adhesives for gluing wood are urea-formaldehyde resins. Ammonium salts (e.g. NH₄Cl) are generally used as curing aids. The dataset is from the reception at the factory gate of all materials and fuels used, to plywood produced at the factory gate. The dataset includes the inputs to and outputs of the production processes and the available process emissions (Wernet et al., 2016). Table 11 shows the LCI of the production of 1 m³ of softwood or hardwood veneer plywood.

Table 11. LCI of the production of 1 m³ of softwood or hardwood veneer plywood.

Flow	Source
INPUT	
Wood resources	
Sawlogs and veneer logs softwood	Ecoinvent (based on softwood forestry, spruce/pine, sustainable forest management sawlog and veneer log, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, U – DE/SE)
Sawlogs and veneer logs hardwood	Ecoinvent (based on hardwood forestry, birch, sustainable forest management sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, U – SE; hardwood forestry, oak, sustainable forest management sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, U – DE; hardwood forestry, beech, sustainable forest management sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, U - DE)
Transportation	Ecoinvent (based on market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cutoff, U – RER) and own assumption on average transport distances (Table 7)
Electricity, medium voltage	Ecoinvent (based on market for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, S – EE/DE)
Fuels	
Heating oil	Ecoinvent (based on heat production, light fuel oil, at industrial furnace 1MW heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Industrial by-products (own production)	Ecoinvent (based on Carbon dioxide, non-fossil, resource correction. This exchange has been added after economic allocation in order to re-balance the non-fossil carbon dioxide resource extraction)
Operating resources	
Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin, RER	Ecoinvent (based on elementary flow)
Tap water	Ecoinvent (based on market group for tap water tap water Cutoff, S – RER)

Diesel	Ecoinvent (based on diesel production, petroleum refinery operation diesel Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Lubricating oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for lubricating oil lubricating oil Cutoff, S - RER)
Cutting materials	Ecoinvent (based on market for steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled Cutoff, S – GLO)
Binder materials	
Synthetic rubber	Ecoinvent (based on market group for tap water tap water Cutoff, S – RER)
Urea formaldehyde resin	Ecoinvent (based on market for urea formaldehyde resin urea formaldehyde resin Cutoff, S – RER)

Flow	Source
OUTPUT	
Plywood	1 m ³
Wood ash mixture, pure	Ecoinvent (based on market for wood ash mixture, pure wood ash mixture, pure Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Waste mineral oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for waste mineral oil waste mineral oil Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Wastewater from plywood production	Ecoinvent (based on market for wastewater from plywood production wastewater from plywood production Cutoff, S – GLO)
Waste rubber, unspecified	Ecoinvent (based on market for waste rubber, unspecified waste rubber, unspecified Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Municipal solid waste	Ecoinvent (based on market group for municipal solid waste municipal solid waste Cutoff, U - RER)
Scrap steel	Ecoinvent (based on market for scrap steel scrap steel Cutoff, S – RoW)
Emissions to air, soil and water	Elementary flows

3.3.2.3 Poles and stakes industry

Poles and stakes softwood/hardwood

According to the MFA results, poles and stakes from softwood are produced CSR 1 (Estonia) and CSR 3 (Catalonia) and for hardwood only in CSR 3 (Catalonia) (Table 8). Within the LCI it was assumed that the technology and the share of processed softwood species as well as the share of hardwood species was the same among regions. According to the regional background system, the processes of transportation and electricity production were adapted to regional characteristics of the CSRs. If applicable, within the global background system data sets presenting the European average without Switzerland were used, otherwise global data sets were used (see Figure A. 4 in Appendix A).

Specifics of the poles and stakes softwood/hardwood and its life cycle

The production process of poles and stakes (see Figure A. 4 in Appendix A), includes debarking, open-air drying, dressing and treatment with preservatives (creosote), impregnating the poles and stakes within the preservatives.

The process debarking and dressing were modelled using the inventory model of wooden poles made by (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009). For open-air drying, the predefined dataset of Ecoinvent called “beam, softwood/hardwood, raw, air drying to u=20% | sawnwood, beam, softwood, raw, dried (u=20%) | Cutoff, U” was used. This dataset represents the natural air-drying process of softwood beam per m³ dried wood. The process was adapted using the input and output data from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009). After the debarking the poles and stakes are dried. Air drying occurs during storage, which is assumed to take place on-site. Poles and stakes are dried for 12 months (Wernet et al., 2016).

For treatment impregnation of poles and stakes with preservatives, the predefined dataset of Ecoinvent called “wood preservation, hot/cold dipping, creosote, outdoor use, ground contact | wood preservation, hot/cold dipping, creosote, outdoor use, ground contact | Cutoff, U” was used. The hot/cold dipping process or hot-cold bath as a batch process involves placing wood in a tank of hot preservative oil followed by immersion in cold preservatives. The hot bath increases the viscosity of the wood preservative and therefore improves penetration into the wood. This hot/cold dipping process is frequently used in treating the butt-ends of fruit tree and vine posts or utility poles with creosote that will have ground contact (Wernet et al., 2016). Table 12 shows the LCI of the production of 1 m³ softwood or hardwood poles and stakes.

Table 12. LCI of the production of 1 m³ of softwood or hardwood poles and stakes.

Flow	Source
INPUT	
Debarking	Based on (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)
Power for debarking (electricity, medium voltage)	Ecoinvent (based on market for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, S, EE/ES) Amounts from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)
Sawlogs and veneer logs softwood	Ecoinvent (based on softwood forestry, spruce/pine, sustainable forest management sawlog and veneer log, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, U – DE/SE) Amounts from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)
Sawlogs and veneer logs hardwood	Ecoinvent (based on hardwood forestry, birch, sustainable forest management sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, U – SE; hardwood forestry, oak, sustainable forest management sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, U – DE; hardwood forestry, beech, sustainable forest management sawlog and veneer log, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, U - DE) Amounts from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)
Transportation of sawlogs and veneer logs softwood and hardwood	Ecoinvent (based on market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cutoff, U – RER) and own assumption on average transport distances (Table 7)
Open-air drying	
Debarked logs	From debarking process Amounts from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)
Occupation, industrial area	Ecoinvent (based on beam, softwood/hardwood, raw, air drying to u=20% sawnwood, beam, softwood, raw, dried (u=20%) Cutoff, U)
Transformation, from unspecified	Ecoinvent (based on beam, softwood/hardwood, raw, air drying to u=20% sawnwood, beam, softwood, raw, dried (u=20%) Cutoff, U)
Transformation, to industrial area	Ecoinvent (based on beam, softwood/hardwood, raw, air drying to u=20% sawnwood, beam, softwood, raw, dried (u=20%) Cutoff, U)
Dressing	
Dried logs	From process Open-air drying process. Amounts from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)
Power for dressing (electricity, medium voltage)	Ecoinvent (based on market for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, S – EE/ES) Amounts from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)
Heat from dressing (heat, district or industrial natural gas)	Ecoinvent (based on heat and power co-generation, natural gas, conventional power plant, 100MW electrical heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cutoff, S – EE/ES) Amounts from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)
Preservation (impregnation)	
Dressed poles and stakes	From process dressing process. Amounts from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)
Power for impregnation (electricity, medium voltage)	Ecoinvent (based on market for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, S – EE/ES) Amounts from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)

Heat from dressing (heat, district or industrial natural gas)	Ecoinvent (based on heat and power co-generation, natural gas, conventional power plant, 100MW electrical heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cutoff, S- EE/ES) Amounts from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)
Lubricating oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for lubricating oil lubricating oil Cutoff, S – RER) Amounts from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)
Wood preservation facility, hot/cold dipping tank	Ecoinvent (based on market for wood preservation facility, hot/cold dipping tank wood preservation facility, hot/cold dipping tank Cutoff, U – GLO)
Wood preservative, creosote	Ecoinvent (based on market for wood preservative, creosote wood preservative, creosote Cutoff, U – RER) Amounts from (Erlandsson and Almemark, 2009)

Flow	Source
OUTPUT	
Softwood/hardwood poles and stakes	1 m ³
Waste mineral oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for waste mineral oil waste mineral oil Cutoff, U - Europe without Switzerland)
Emissions to air, soil and water	Elementary flows

3.3.2.4 Pulp production (kraft or sulphate process)

Pulp production (kraft or sulphate process)

Two major different processes are applied to produce wood pulp: the kraft process/sulphate process and the sulphite process. The sulphite process is not present in any of the four CSRs. The kraft process is present in CSR 1 (Estonia) and CSR 4 (Hesse, Thuringia). Within the LCI, it was assumed that the technology and the share of processed hardwood and softwood species is the same among regions. According to the regional background system, the processes of transportation, fuel production and electricity production were adapted to regional characteristics of the CSRs as far as regional providers were available. If applicable, within the global background system data sets presenting the European average were used. Otherwise, global data sets were used (see Figure A.4 in Appendix A).

Specifics of pulp production (kraft or sulphate process) and its life cycle

The Ecoinvent v3.8 database offers a predefined dataset of the kraft process (Wernet et al., 2016). This dataset represents an aggregation of the production of Elemental Chlorine Free (ECF) and Totally Chlorine Free (TCF) kraft pulp, obtained from northern European hardwood/softwood in 2017. Industry data used was provided by the European Pulp Industry Sector (EPIS). The used values are a weighted average of all corresponding pulp mills. The represented technology is considered state of the art for an European average. Pulp is a clean, wood-based, renewable and biodegradable raw material to make different paper, board and other products. The pulp, or fibres from the wood are separated in a kraft cooking process in a so-called fibre line. In a recovery line, the chemicals used in the cooking process are recovered to be used again and energy is produced. The third process is effluent treatment where gaseous and liquid discharges to the environment are continuously minimized and monitored. Softwood pulp is made from coniferous trees, most typically from different species of pine and spruce. Hardwood pulp is made from non-coniferous trees, in Nordic countries primarily of birch. The process starts with the transport of the wood to the pulp factory. The process includes transports to the pulp mill, wood handling, chemical pulping and bleaching, drying process, energy production on-site, recovery cycles of chemicals and internal wastewater treatment. Only key emission factors were provided by the industry, the remaining

emissions from on-site energy production from externally supplied fuels were calculated, using emission profiles from Ecoinvent combustion processes. Moreover, the following "internal" biogenic fuels are represented by the calculated emissions but do not have the corresponding fuel input from technosphere, because they are supplied from within the system boundaries: Biogas: 0.00183785 m³, bark/other woods or biomass: 1.3316507 MJ (aggregation of external and internal wood similar biofuels, energy density used: 16.75 MJ/kg), methanol: 0.00801684 m³. The following biofuels were not included in the emission approximation due to a likely mismatch of the emission of a black liquor boiler and wood chips combustion and for the lack of an appropriate proxy: black liquor, tall oil pitch and sludge. The activity ends when the kraft pulp is ready to be sold (Wernet et al., 2016).

For the visualization of the production process, mainly (Suhr et al., 2015) was used (see Figure A. 5) Figure A. 5. Foreground and background system of pulp production (kraft or sulfate process). The visualization also shows the possibility of further processing the pulp into paper. In this case, the pulp is not dried but fed directly into paper production. In the LCA, the option of dried market kraft pulp is considered as the end product. Table 13 shows the LCI of the production of 1 kg of marketed kraft pulp.

Table 13. LCI of the production of 1 kg of dry market kraft pulp.

Flow	Source
INPUT	
Wood resources	
Pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark	Ecoinvent (based on hardwood forestry, birch, sustainable forest management pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S - RoW)
Pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark	Ecoinvent (based on softwood forestry, spruce, sustainable forest management pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S - DE/RoW; softwood forestry, pine, sustainable forest management pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S - DE/RoW)
Wood chips, dry, measured as dry mass	Ecoinvent (based on market for wood chips, dry, measured as dry mass wood chips, dry, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - RER)
Residual softwood, wet	Ecoinvent (based on market for residual softwood, wet residual softwood, wet Cutoff, S - RER)
Transportation of softwood and hardwood	Ecoinvent (based on market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cutoff, S - RER) and own assumption on average transport distances (Table 7)
Electricity, high voltage	Ecoinvent (based on market for electricity, high voltage electricity, high voltage Cutoff, S - EE/DE)
Fuels	
Heavy fuel oil	Ecoinvent (based on market group for heavy fuel oil heavy fuel oil Cutoff, S - RER)
Light fuel oil	Ecoinvent (based on market group for light fuel oil light fuel oil Cutoff, S - RER)
Natural gas, high pressure	Ecoinvent (based on market group for natural gas, high pressure natural gas, high pressure Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Operating resources	
Water, unspecified natural origin	Ecoinvent (Elementary flows/Resource/in water)
Malusil	Ecoinvent (based on market for malusil malusil Cutoff, S - GLO)
Quicklime, milled, loose	Ecoinvent (based on market for quicklime, milled, loose quicklime, milled, loose Cutoff, U - RoW)
Sand	Ecoinvent (based on market for sand sand Cutoff, S - RoW)
Chemicals	
Calcium carbonate, precipitated	Ecoinvent (based on market for calcium carbonate, precipitated calcium carbonate, precipitated Cutoff, S - RER)
Carbon dioxide, non-fossil, resource correction	Ecoinvent (Elementary flows/Resource/in air)
Chemical, organic	Ecoinvent (based on market for chemical, organic chemical, organic Cutoff, S - GLO)

EDTA, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid	Ecoinvent (based on market for EDTA, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid EDTA, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid Cutoff, S – GLO)
Hydrogen peroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	Ecoinvent (based on market for hydrogen peroxide, without water, in 50% solution state hydrogen peroxide, without water, in 50% solution state Cutoff, S – RER)
Magnesium sulfate	Ecoinvent (based on market for magnesium sulfate magnesium sulfate Cutoff, S – GLO)
Methanol, from biomass	Ecoinvent (based on market for methanol, from biomass methanol, from biomass Cutoff, S – RoW)
Oxygen, liquid	Ecoinvent (based on air separation, cryogenic oxygen, liquid Cutoff, S – RoW)
Sodium chlorate, powder	Ecoinvent (based on market for sodium chlorate, powder sodium chlorate, powder Cutoff, S – RER)
Sodium formate	market for sodium formate sodium formate Cutoff, S - RER
Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	Ecoinvent (based on market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state Cutoff, S – GLO)
Sodium sulfate, anhydrite	Ecoinvent (based on market for sodium sulfate, anhydrite sodium sulfate, anhydrite Cutoff, S – RER)
Sulfur dioxide, liquid	Ecoinvent (based on market for sulfur dioxide, liquid sulfur dioxide, liquid Cutoff, S – RER)
Sulfuric acid	Ecoinvent (based on market for sulfuric acid sulfuric acid Cutoff, S – RER)

Flow	Source
OUTPUT	
Sulfate pulp, bleached	1 kg
Emissions to air and water	Ecoinvent (Elementary flows)
Limestone residue	Ecoinvent (based on market for limestone residue limestone residue Cutoff, S – RoW)
Municipal solid waste	Ecoinvent (based on market group for municipal solid waste municipal solid waste Cutoff, S – RER)
Sludge from pulp and paper production	Ecoinvent (based on market for sludge from pulp and paper production sludge from pulp and paper production Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Waste mineral oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for waste mineral oil waste mineral oil Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Water	Ecoinvent (Elementary flows/Emission to air/unspecified)
Water	Ecoinvent (Elementary flows/Emission to water/unspecified)
Emissions to air and water	Elementary flows
Wastes for waste treatment	
Digester sludge	Ecoinvent (based on digester sludge, Recycled Content cut-off digester sludge Cutoff, S – GLO)
EDTA, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid	Ecoinvent (based on market for EDTA, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid EDTA, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid Cutoff, S – GLO)
Electricity, high voltage	Ecoinvent (based on market for electricity, high voltage electricity, high voltage Cutoff, S – EE)

3.3.2.5 Thermomechanical pulp process

Thermomechanical pulp production

According to MFA results, thermo mechanical pulp is produced in the CSR 1. According to the regional background system, the processes of transportation and electricity production were adapted to regional characteristics of the CSRs. If applicable, within the global background system data sets presenting the European average without Switzerland were used, otherwise global data sets were used (see Figure A. 6 in Appendix A).

Specifics of thermomechanical pulp production and its life cycle

The predefined dataset of Ecoinvent v3.8 provides a general thermomechanical pulp production. This dataset characterizes the average production of mechanical pulp following a refiner process with thermal pre-treatment (TMP) in Europe. Bleaching has not been included because mechanical pulps cannot be brightened effectively by oxidative and reductive bleaching, and because the thermomechanical pulp has other uses besides making paper such as, input for the fibreboards production. The activity starts with the transport of the wood to the pulp factory. The process includes transports to the pulp mill, raw material handling, pulping, drying, recovery cycles of chemicals and internal wastewater treatment. The activity ends when the thermomechanical pulp is ready to be sold (Wernet et al., 2016).

In addition, the processes of debarking and chipping were based on the dataset of Ecoinvent v3.8 called “wood chips production, hardwood, at sawmill | wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass | Cutoff, U”, which was adapted using LCI data from (Gontia and Janssen, 2016). It was included the recovered heat from bark and wood chips provided by (Gontia and Janssen, 2016). Table 14 shows the LCI of the production of 1 kg thermomechanical pulp.

Table 14. LCI of the production of 1 kg of thermomechanical pulp.

Flow	Source
INPUT	
Wood chips production	
Pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark	Ecoinvent (based on hardwood forestry, oak, sustainable forest management pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, U – DE; hardwood forestry, beech, sustainable forest management pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, U – DE; hardwood forestry, birch, sustainable forest management pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, U – SE)
Transportation of pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark	Ecoinvent (based on market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cutoff, U – RER) and own assumption on average transport distances (Table 7 Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.)
Lubricating oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for lubricating oil lubricating oil Cutoff, U - RER)
Heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas (recovered heat from bark and wood chips)	Ecoinvent (market for market group for heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas Cutoff, S – RER) Amounts from (Gontia and Janssen, 2016).
Electricity, medium voltage	Ecoinvent (based on market group for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, U - Europe without Switzerland) Amounts from (Gontia and Janssen, 2016).
Steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled	Ecoinvent (based on market for steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled Cutoff, U – GLO)
Chipper, stationary, electric	Ecoinvent (based on market for chipper, stationary, electric chipper, stationary, electric Cutoff, U – GLO)
Thermomechanical pulp production	
Wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass	From wood chips production process. Amounts from (Gontia and Janssen, 2016).
Electricity, medium voltage	Ecoinvent (based on market group for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, U - Europe without Switzerland) Amounts from (Gontia and Janssen, 2016).
Heat, district or industrial, natural gas	Ecoinvent (based on market for heat, district or industrial, natural gas heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland) Amounts from (Gontia and Janssen, 2016).
Heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas (recovered heat from thermo mechanical pulp production)	Ecoinvent (based on market group for heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas Cutoff, S – RER) Amounts from (Gontia and Janssen, 2016).
Water cooling, unspecified natural origin	Ecoinvent (based on thermomechanical pulp production thermomechanical pulp Cutoff, U)

Water, unspecified natural origin	Ecoinvent (based on thermomechanical pulp production thermomechanical pulp Cutoff, U)
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Flow	Source
OUTPUT	
Thermomechanical pulp	1 kg
Municipal solid waste	Ecoinvent (based on market group for municipal solid waste municipal solid waste Cutoff, U - RER)
Scrap steel	Ecoinvent (based market for scrap steel scrap steel Cutoff, U - Europe without Switzerland)
Waste wood, untreated	Ecoinvent (based on market group for waste wood, untreated waste wood, untreated Cutoff, U - RER)
Wood ash, mixture, pure	Ecoinvent (based on market for wood ash mixture, pure wood ash mixture, pure Cutoff, U - Europe without Switzerland)
Emissions to air, soil and water	Elementary flows

3.3.2.6 Particleboard production

Difference among case study regions

In CSR 1 and in CSR 4 particleboard production is present. The main difference between the two CSRs is the manufactured resources. While in the CSR 1 only fresh wood fibre or industrial by-products are processed to obtain high quality particleboards, in CSR 4 up to 30-40% of used wood fibres coming from post-consumer wood chips are used.

However, within the LCI, it was assumed that the technology is the same. According to the regional background system, the processes of transportation, fuel production, and electricity production were adapted to regional characteristics of the CSRs. If applicable, within the global background system data sets presenting the European average were used, otherwise global data sets were used (see Figure A. 7 in Appendix A).

Specifics of the particleboard and its life cycle

Particleboard is manufactured by mixing different wood by-products, fresh wood fibres and optional post-consumer wood chips together with a resin and afterwards, forming the mix into a sheet. The raw material to be used for the particles is fed into a disc chipper. The particles are first dried, after which any oversized or undersized particles are screened out. Resin, in liquid form, is then sprayed through nozzles onto the particles. There are several types of resins that are commonly used (e.g. amino formaldehyde-based resins, urea melamine resins, phenol formaldehyde, melamine urea phenolic formaldehyde resins) depending on the specific application. The particleboards are pressed in two steps and afterwards cooled down. Finally, the shape is given by sanding and trimming. The density of standard particleboard can vary between 650–750 kg/m³. Typical thickness is in a range of 3 to > 40 mm. The used dataset of particleboard production is provided by Ecoinvent v3.8 based on data of the European Panel Federation (EPF). The data set was modified to meet the ONEforest CSR-specific fore- and background systems. It was assumed that the volume of post-consumer wood chips in the predefined data set is equally distributed to softwood and hardwood pulpwood in Estonia. This was in line with the share of pulpwood used in the particleboard industry which was applied in the herein conducted MFA (see Chapter 4.1.1 CSR 1 Estonia).

Table 15 shows the LCI of the production of 1 m³ uncoated particleboard.

Table 15. LCI of the production of 1 m³ uncoated particleboard.

Flow	Source
INPUT	
Wood resources	
Pulpwood hardwood under bark	Ecoinvent (based on hardwood forestry, birch, sustainable forest management pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S – SE, hardwood forestry, beech, sustainable forest management pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S – DE, hardwood forestry, oak, sustainable forest management pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S - DE)
Pulpwood softwood under bark	Ecoinvent (based on softwood forestry, pine/spruce, sustainable forest management pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S – SE/DE)
By-products from different wood processing industries (wood chips, slabs, siding)	Ecoinvent (based on market for slab and siding, softwood, wet, measured as dry mass slab and siding, softwood, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland, market for wood chips, dry, measured as dry mass wood chips, dry, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - RER)
Wood chips from forests or from sawing, hardwood and softwood)	Ecoinvent (based on softwood forestry, pine, sustainable forest management wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S – DE, wood chips production, softwood, at sawmill wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland, hardwood forestry, birch, sustainable forest management wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S – SE, hardwood forestry, oak, sustainable forest management wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S – DE, softwood forestry, spruce, sustainable forest management wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S – SE, softwood forestry, pine, sustainable forest management wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S – SE, hardwood forestry, beech, sustainable forest management wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S – DE, softwood forestry, spruce, sustainable forest management wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S – DE, wood chips production, hardwood, at sawmill wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Post-consumer wood chips (only for CSR4)	Ecoinvent (based on market for wood chips, from post-consumer wood, measured as dry mass wood chips, from post-consumer wood, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S – RER)
Transportation	Ecoinvent (based on market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cutoff, U - RER) and own assumption on average transport distances (Table 7)
Electricity, medium voltage	Ecoinvent (based on country-specific market for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, S - EE/DE)
Fuels	
Sawdust	Ecoinvent (based on market for sawdust, wet, measured as dry mass sawdust, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Natural gas	Ecoinvent (based on heat production, heavy fuel oil, at industrial furnace 1MW heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Heavy fuel oil	Ecoinvent (based on heat production, heavy fuel oil, at industrial furnace 1MW heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas Cutoff, U - Europe without Switzerland)
Light fuel oil	Ecoinvent (based on heat production, light fuel oil, at industrial furnace 1MW heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Operating resources	
Tap water	Ecoinvent (based on market group for tap water tap water Cutoff, S - RER)
Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin	Elementary flow
Water, well, in ground	Elementary flow
Diesel	Ecoinvent (based on market for diesel, burned in building machine diesel, burned in building machine Cutoff, S - GLO)
Lubricating oil	Ecoinvent (based market for lubricating oil lubricating oil Cutoff, S - RER)

Binder and additives	
Aluminium sulphate, powder	Ecoinvent (based on market for aluminium sulfate, powder aluminium sulfate, powder Cutoff, S - RER)
Chemical, organic	Ecoinvent (based on market for chemical, organic chemical, organic Cutoff, S - GLO)
Melamine formaldehyde resin	Ecoinvent (based on market for melamine formaldehyde resin melamine formaldehyde resin Cutoff, S - RER)
Methylene diphenyl diisocyanate	Ecoinvent (based on market for methylene diphenyl diisocyanate methylene diphenyl diisocyanate Cutoff, S - RER)
Paraffin	Ecoinvent (based on market for paraffin paraffin Cutoff, S - GLO)
Phenolic resin	Ecoinvent (based on market for phenolic resin phenolic resin Cutoff, S - RER)
Urea	Ecoinvent (based on market for urea urea Cutoff, S - RER)
Urea formaldehyde resin	Ecoinvent (based on market for urea formaldehyde resin urea formaldehyde resin Cutoff, S - RER)

Flow	Source
OUTPUT	
Particleboard raw	1 m ³
Biowaste	Ecoinvent (based on market for biowaste biowaste Cutoff, S - RoW)
Hazardous waste for incineration	Ecoinvent (based on market for hazardous waste, for incineration hazardous waste, for incineration Cutoff, U - RoW)
Wood ash mixture pure	Ecoinvent (based on market for wood ash mixture, pure wood ash mixture, pure Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Waste water from particleboard production	Ecoinvent (based on market for wastewater from particleboard production wastewater from particleboard production Cutoff, S - GLO)
Emissions to air, soil and water	Elementary flows

3.3.2.7 OSB production

Difference among case study regions

Among all CSRs, oriented strand boards (OSB) are only produced in CSR 1. According to the regional background system, the processes of transportation, fuel production, and electricity production were adapted to regional characteristics of the CSR. If applicable, within the global background system data sets presenting the European average were used, otherwise global data sets were used (see Figure A. 8 in Appendix A).

Specifics of the particleboard and its life cycle

The core process of OSB production is the strander which produces strands. The strands are flaked from round wood and must have a particular size and shape. They retain the natural strength properties and they determine the quality of the finished product. The strands are dried and afterwards blended with wax and resin. The strands must be orientated in a particular direction in the two outer layers, and sometimes in all three layers. The resin/wax bonds the strands in the pressing process. The coated strands are then conveyed to the forming line and cut to size. Afterwards the mat is pressed, under high temperature and pressure and finished to an OSB. Finally, the OSB is trimmed and cut to produce the finished OSB board.

The herein applied dataset was taken from Ecoinvent v3.8 and represents the average of production of oriented strand board production of EPF members. It ranges from the reception at the gate of all materials and fuels used including their impacts. The process ends with the uncoated oriented strand board at gate.

Table 16 shows the LCI of the production of 1 m³ OSB.

Table 16. LCI of the production of 1 m³ OSB.

Flow	Source
INPUT	
Wood resources	
Pulpwood softwood under bark	Ecoinvent (based on softwood forestry, pine/spruce, sustainable forest management pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S – SE/DE)
Transportation	Ecoinvent (based on market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cutoff, U - RER) and own assumption on average transport distances (Table 7)
Electricity, medium voltage	Ecoinvent (based on market for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, S - EE)
Fuels	
Natural gas	Ecoinvent (based on heat production, heavy fuel oil, at industrial furnace 1MW heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Light fuel oil	Ecoinvent (based on heat production, light fuel oil, at industrial furnace 1MW heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Operating resources	
Tap water	Ecoinvent (based on market group for tap water tap water Cutoff, S - RER)
Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin	Elementary flow
Diesel	Ecoinvent (based on market for diesel, burned in building machine diesel, burned in building machine Cutoff, S - GLO)
Lubricating oil	Ecoinvent (based market for lubricating oil lubricating oil Cutoff, S - RER)
Binder and additives	
Chemical, organic	Ecoinvent (based on market for chemical, organic chemical, organic Cutoff, S - GLO)
Methylene diphenyl diisocyanate	Ecoinvent (based on market for methylene diphenyl diisocyanate methylene diphenyl diisocyanate Cutoff, S - RER)
Paraffin	Ecoinvent (based on market for paraffin paraffin Cutoff, S - GLO)

Flow	Source
OUTPUT	
Oriented strand board	1 m ³
Biowaste	Ecoinvent (based on market for biowaste biowaste Cutoff, S – RoW)
Wood ash mixture pure	Ecoinvent (based on market for wood ash mixture, pure wood ash mixture, pure Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Emissions to air, soil and water	Elementary flows

3.3.2.8 MDF, HDF, LDF, and other fibreboards production

Medium density fibreboards

With reference to the MFA results, MDF, HDF, LDF, and other fibreboards are produced in CSR 1 and CSR 4. For the LCI, it was assumed that MDF production is considered representative of MDF, HDF, LDF, and other fibreboards production. Regarding the background systems, the electricity grid mix (medium voltage), heat generation and pulpwood transport are adjusted at the CSR-specific level. Other inputs of the background system are based on European datasets (without Switzerland), in exceptions global datasets were used. From the resource softwood and hardwood pulpwood, all ancillary inputs such as energy, heat, paraffin, urea, urea formaldehyde resin, water, and fuels are modelled from the cradle to the factory gate. Activity ends with the uncoated medium density board at the factory gate. The defined functional unit is 1 m³ uncoated MDF.

Specifics of the MDF production

For the LCI modelling of MDF production, an Ecoinvent v3.8 dataset was used that represents medium density fibreboards (MDF) production as a weighted average of medium density panels produced by the members of EPF (Table 17). The MDF fibreboards has a density of 684 kg/m³ (546 kg/m³ wood content, 7% moisture). Raw material such as clean wood chips and other wooden materials (dust, strips, etc.) are softened in a steam-pressurized digester and refiner to fibres suitable for making the board. The fibres are then dried and blended to reduce the moisture content and to mix them with resin, wax, and any other additives. The mixed fibres are transported to a forming machine where they are pre-pressed before they enter to a hot press. After pressing, the mats are trimmed, cooled and sanded before cutting into size (see Figure A. 1 in Appendix A).

Table 17. LCI of the production of 1 m³ MDF.

Flow	Source
INPUT	
Wood resources	
Pulpwood hardwood under bark	Ecoinvent (based on hardwood forestry, oak, sustainable forest management pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S – DE; hardwood forestry, beech, sustainable forest management pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S – DE; hardwood forestry, birch, sustainable forest management pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S – SE)
Pulpwood softwood under bark	Ecoinvent (based on softwood forestry, pine/spruce, sustainable forest management pulpwood, softwood, measured as solid wood under bark Cutoff, S – SE/DE)
Industrial by-products, softwood (wood chips, slabs and siding)	Ecoinvent (based on market for industrial by-products as wood chips Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland) Ecoinvent (based on market for industrial by-products as slabs and siding, softwood Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Transportation	Ecoinvent (based on market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cutoff, U - RER) and own assumption on average transport distances (Table 7)
Electricity, medium voltage	Ecoinvent (based on market for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, S – EE/DE)
Heat and fuels	
Natural gas	Ecoinvent (based on heat production, natural gas, at boiler condensing modulating > 100 kW heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Light fuel oil	Ecoinvent (based on heat production, light fuel oil, at boiler condensing modulating > 100 kW heat, district or industrial, light fuel oil Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Heavy fuel oil	Ecoinvent (based on heat production, heavy fuel oil, at boiler condensing modulating > 100 kW heat, district or industrial, heavy fuel oil Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Sawdust	Ecoinvent (based on market for saw dust saw dust, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Operating resources	
Tap water	Ecoinvent (based on market group for tap water tap water Cutoff, S - Europe)
Cooling water	elementary flow
Water, from ground, well	elementary flow
Water, river	elementary flow
Diesel	Ecoinvent (based on market for diesel diesel burned in machine Cutoff-S – GLO)
Lubricating oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for lubricating oil lubricating oil Cutoff, S - RER)
Binder and additives	
Aluminium sulfate, powder	Ecoinvent (based on market for aluminium sulfate, powder aluminium sulfate, powder Cutoff, S - RER)
Chemical, organic	Ecoinvent (based on market for chemical, organic chemical, organic Cutoff, S - GLO)

Melamine formaldehyde resin	Ecoinvent (based on melamine formaldehyde resin production melamine formaldehyde resin Cutoff, S - RER)
Paraffin	Ecoinvent (based on paraffin production paraffin Cutoff, S - RER)
Urea	Ecoinvent (based on urea production urea Cutoff, S - RER)
Urea formaldehyde resin	Ecoinvent (based on urea formaldehyde resin production urea formaldehyde resin Cutoff, S - RER)

Flow	Source
OUTPUT	
MDF	1 m ³
Biowaste	Ecoinvent (based on market for biowaste biowaste Cutoff, S - GLO)
Hazardous waste for incineration	Ecoinvent (based on market for hazardous waste, for incineration hazardous waste, for incineration Cutoff, S – Europe without Switzerland)
Wood ash mixture pure	Ecoinvent (based on treatment of wood ash mixture in incineration wood ash mixture, pure Cutoff, S - RER) Ecoinvent (based on treatment of wood ash mixture in landfill wood ash mixture, pure Cutoff, S - RER)
Waste water	Ecoinvent (based on waste water treatment from MDF production waste water from MDF production Cutoff, S - RER)
Emissions to air, soil and water	Elementary flows

3.3.2.9 Pellets production

Pellets

The process for pellet production is called pelletizing. Pelletizing is used in many different areas, such as fuel preparation (e.g. wood pellets) for the conditioning of raw materials. The purpose is to improve the handling of the pelletized material, e.g., by increasing density, avoiding dust, and/or improving dosage. Pellets are produced in CSR 1, 3 and 4. CSR 2 does not have a pellet production facility. There are two forms of pellets on the market: industrial pellets and norm-pellets. Whereas industrial pellets are larger and have also bark as a raw material, norm-pellets are mainly made from sawmilling residues (sawdust). Industrial pellets are burned in industrial size furnaces, norm-pellets are in most cases used in household fireplaces or modern pellet boilers.

In CSR 3 and 4 only pellet mills for norm-pellets are installed, in CSR 1 norm-pellets as well as industrial pellets are produced. Here also roundwood is chipped and the green wood chips are milled, grinded and sieved to be pressed to industrial pellets. Therefore, the LCI has been adapted for CSR 1 in order to present two flows for industrial and norm-pellets.

Specifics of the product/life cycle

The transport to the end-consumer has not been assessed in this study, but it can be assumed that the transport also has another impact on the environment and therefore would change the result of the LCA. Especially in countries, where the pellets are often exported, this can have an impact. The process of the pellet production is shown in Figure A. 10, in Appendix A. Table 18 shows the LCI of the production of 1 kg of pellets.

Table 18. LCI of the production of 1 kg of pellets.

Flow	Source
INPUT	
Wood resources	
Sawdust	Ecoinvent (based on market for sawdust, wet, measured as dry mass sawdust, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)

Shavings hardwood	Ecoinvent (based on market for shavings, hardwood, measured as dry mass shavings, hardwood, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Shavings softwood	Ecoinvent (based on market for shavings, softwood, measured as dry mass shavings, softwood, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Wood chips	Ecoinvent (based on market for wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Transportation	Ecoinvent (based on market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cutoff, U - RER) and own assumption on average transport distances (Table 7)
Electricity, medium voltage	Ecoinvent (based on market group for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Heat	Ecoinvent (based on market group for heat, central or small-scale, other than natural gas heat, central or small-scale, other than natural gas Cutoff, S - RER)
Operating resources	
Water	Ecoinvent (based on wood pellet production wood pellet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, U)
Diesel	Ecoinvent (based on wood pellet production wood pellet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, U)
Lubricating oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for lubricating oil lubricating oil Cutoff, S – RER)

Flow	Source
	OUTPUT
Wood pellet	1 t
Waste mineral oil	Ecoinvent (based on market for waste mineral oil waste mineral oil Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Emissions to air, soil and water	Elementary flow

3.3.2.10 Briquettes production

Briquettes

Briquettes are – in comparison to pellets – larger and cuboid. Pellets are used for mechanized filling of boilers due to their smaller size and conditions. The briquettes are, since they are larger, easier to produce and to transport. Also, on the market are briquettes, which are made of lignite and hard coal. In this study, only briquettes made out wood chips were considered. In this project's CSR, briquettes from woody resources are only produced in CSR 1.

Specifics of the product/life cycle

The transport to the end-consumer has not been assessed in this study, but it can be assumed that the transport causes additional impacts on the environment and therefore would change the results of the LCA. Also, the by-products of the process were not taken into consideration, since the by-products (oils, gas etc.) are not always collected and used. Especially, if the by-products are used, this could have a positive impact on the LCA. Data sources for the LCI of briquette processes are only scarcely available. The most recent study on this topic is from the US Department of Agriculture (US Department of Agriculture, 2016), which also provides a dataset for a LCI. Although process data has been collected in California, the process of the briquette production does not differ to European production units. In this process dataset, a RUF Briquetting Systems from a Company in Germany was used. The woody resources and the energy inputs were adapted to European conditions, though. Transportation, debarking, the waste mineral oil and water were assumed to have a similar impact as in the pellet process and were used as a data input. The process of the briquette production is shown in Figure A. 11, in Appendix A Table 19 shows the LCI of the production of 1 t of briquettes.

Table 19. LCI of the production of 1 t of briquettes.

Flow	Source
INPUT	
Wood resources	
Debarking	Ecoinvent (based on debarking, softwood, in forest bark chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, U)
Wood chips	wood chip briquette production; at plant, USDA's Open Research Data market for wood chips and particles, willow wood chips and particles, willow Cutoff, S – RER market for wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland
Transportation	Ecoinvent (based on market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cutoff, U - RER) and own assumption on average transport distances (Table 7)
Electricity, medium voltage	wood chip briquette production; at plant, USDA's Open Research Data (US Department of Agriculture, 2016)
Heat	wood chip briquette production; at plant, USDA's Open Research Data from (US Department of Agriculture, 2016)
Operating resources	
Water	wood chip briquette production; at plant, USDA's Open Research Data (US Department of Agriculture, 2016)
Diesel	wood chip briquette production; at plant, USDA's Open Research Data from (US Department of Agriculture, 2016)
Lubricating oil	wood chip briquette production; at plant, USDA's Open Research Data (US Department of Agriculture, 2016)

Flow	Source
OUTPUT	
Wood chip briquettes	1 t
Water	Elementary flow
Emissions to air, soil and water	Elementary flow

3.3.2.11 Charcoal production

Charcoal

Charcoal has a long history of usage and is a carbon residue produced by heating wood in an environment of minimal oxygen to remove all water and as much non-carbon content as possible. In the project's CSR, charcoal industry is only produced in CSR 1.

Specifics of the product/life cycle

The transport to the end-consumer has not been assessed in this study, but it can be assumed that the transport also has another impact on the environment and therefore would change the result of LCA. Also, the by-products of the process were not taken into consideration, since the by-products (oils, gas etc.) are not always collected and used. Especially, if the by-products are used, this could have a positive impact on a LCA. The Ecoinvent v3.8 database has a full dataset for charcoal production. The process of the charcoal production is shown in Figure A. 12, in Appendix A.

Table 20 shows the LCI of the production of 1 kg of charcoal.

Table 20. LCI of the production of 1 kg of charcoal.

Flow	Source
INPUT	
Wood resources	

Cleft timber	Ecoinvent (based on market for cleft timber, measured as dry mass cleft timber, measured as dry mass Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Transportation	Ecoinvent (based on market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cutoff, U - RER) and own assumption on average transport distances (Table 7)
Electricity, medium voltage	Ecoinvent (market group for electricity, medium voltage electricity, medium voltage Cutoff, S - Europe without Switzerland)
Heat	Ecoinvent (market group for heat, central or small-scale, other than natural gas heat, central or small-scale, other than natural gas Cutoff, S - RER)
Operating resources	
Water	Ecoinvent (based on charcoal production charcoal Cutoff, U)

Flow	Source
OUTPUT	
Charcoal	1 kg
Water	Elementary flow
Particulates	Elementary flow
Emissions to air, soil and water	Elementary flow

3.3.3 Life cycle impact assessment

To achieve the LCA goal, to provide an environmental impact assessment of the FWVCs, assessing the ecological effects from the forest production to the production of semifinished products, it is needed to select impact assessment method, characterization models, and impact category indicators (ISO 14044, 2020).

Understanding that an LCIA method is a set of LCIA impact categories, the first step was to select an LCIA method. The method selected was CML because it is often applied in many studies and it is recognized as one of the most well-established and world-widely used method, and as the most internationally accepted and recognized applied to wood-based products (Frontera et al., 2020; Klein et al., 2015).

The next step is the selection of characterisation factors. The CML-IA method contains the characterisation factors for all baseline characterisation methods mentioned in the “Handbook on Life Cycle Assessment Guide to the ISO Standards” (Guinée and Lindeijer, 2002), such as global warming potential (GWP), photochemical oxidation, human toxicity and acidification. Moreover, it contains additional characterisation methods, such as Eco-indicator 99 and EPS, and normalization data for all interventions and impact categories (CML-Department of Industrial Ecology, 2016).

The final step is the selection of impact categories. The most examined impact category along the FWVC is GWP (Klein et al., 2015; Kuka et al., 2020; Timmermann and Dibdiakova, 2014), however the FWVC has other environmental impact that can be assessed through other environmental impact categories. In order to give a broad environmental assessment, different categories besides GWP should be considered, only assessing GWP could lead to erroneous conclusions regarding the environmental impacts of the FWVC (Klein et al., 2015; Kuka et al., 2020).

Particulate matter formation potential, agriculture land occupation potential and water depletion potential are often mentioned in public discussion about wood production and utilisation (Höglmeier et al., 2015). However, CML-IA method do not include this impact categories and therefore the method ei-ReCiPe Midpoint (H) was used to assess them. The ReCiPe method main objective is to provide a method that combines CML and Eco-Indicator 99 (Acero et al., 2015).

The impact categories selected are shown in

Table 21, indicating the geographical scale (global, regional and local) of the specific impact category (Henryson et al., 2018; Huijbregts et al., 2016; Stranddorf et al., 2003).

Table 21. Geographical scale of impact categories

Impact categories	Global	Regional	Local
Abiotic depletion potential	✓	✓	✓
Abiotic depletion potential, fossil fuels	✓	✓	✓
Acidification potential		✓	✓
Eutrophication potential	✓	✓	
Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity potential		✓	✓
Global warming potential	✓		
Human toxicity potential		✓	✓
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity potential		✓	✓
Ozone layer depletion potential	✓		
Photochemical oxidation potential		✓	✓
Terrestrial ecotoxicity potential		✓	✓
Particulate matter formation potential	✓	✓	
Agriculture land occupation potential	✓	✓	✓
Water depletion potential	✓	✓	

The selected impact categories are described as followed (Acero et al., 2015; Huijbregts et al., 2016):

- **Abiotic depletion potential.** This impact category refers to the consumption of non-biological resources such as fossil fuels, mineral, metals, water, and others. The value of the abiotic resource consumption of a substance (e.g. lignite or coal) is a measure of the scarcity of a substance. That means it depends on the amount of resources and the extraction rate. It is formed by the amount of resources that are depleted and measured in antimony equivalents (kg Sb eq) and MJ of fossil fuels.
- **Acidification potential.** It is defined as the reduction of the pH due to the acidifying effects of anthropogenic emissions. Acidic gases such as sulphur dioxide (SO₂) react with water in the atmosphere to form acid rain, a process known as acid deposition. Gases that cause acid deposition include ammonia (NH₃), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and sulphur oxides (SO_x). This acid deposition increase acidity in water and soil systems, causing ecosystem impairment. Acidification potential is expressed using the reference unit, kg SO₂ equivalent (kg SO₂ eq).
- **Eutrophication potential.** It is the accumulation of a concentration of chemical nutrients in an ecosystem which leads to abnormal productivity. This causes excessive plant growth like algae in rivers which causes severe reductions in water quality and animal population. This category is expressed using the reference unit, kg PO₄³⁻ equivalents (kg PO₄³⁻ eq).
- **Ecotoxicity potential.** This category is measured as three separate impact categories which examine freshwater, marine and land. The emission of some substances, such as heavy metals, can have impacts on the ecosystem, such as biodiversity loss and/or extinction of species. Characterisation factors are expressed using the reference unit, kg 1,4-dichlorobenzene equivalent (kg 1,4-DB eq), and are measured separately for impacts

of toxic substances on: freshwater aquatic ecosystems, marine ecosystems, and terrestrial ecosystems.

- **Global warming potential** or climate change can be defined as the change in global temperature caused by the greenhouse effect that the release of greenhouse gases by human activity creates. The increase in these emissions is having a noticeable effect on climate, raising the global temperature. It is expected to cause climatic disturbance, desertification, rising sea levels and spread of disease. Factors are expressed as Global Warming Potential over the time horizon of different years, being the most common 100 years (GWP), measured in the reference unit, kg CO₂ equivalent (kg CO₂ eq).
 - **Human toxicity potential.** This category is a calculated index that reflects the potential harm on humans of a unit of chemical released into the environment, and it is based on both the inherent toxicity of a compound and its potential dose. This impact category is measured in kg 1,4- dichlorobenzene equivalents (kg 1,4-DB eq).
 - **Ozone layer depletion potential.** This category is defined as the diminution of the stratospheric ozone layer due to anthropogenic emissions of ozone depleting substances. The major causes of ozone depletion are chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) and hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs). Damage to the ozone layer reduces its ability to prevent ultraviolet (UV) light entering the earth's atmosphere, increasing the amount of carcinogenic UVB light reaching the earth's surface. The characterisation model defines the ozone depletion potential of different gases relative to the reference substance chlorofluorocarbon-11 (CFC-11), expressed in kg CFC-11 equivalent (kg CFC-11 eq).
 - **Photochemical oxidation potential** or photochemical ozone creation potential. This category is defined as type of smog created from effect of sunlight, heat and non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). Photochemical ozone is formed by the reaction of volatile organic compounds and nitrogen oxides in the presence of heat and sunlight. Ozone is protective in the stratosphere, but on the ground-level it is toxic to humans in high concentration. The impact category depends largely on the amounts of carbon monoxide (CO), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxide (NO), ammonium and NMVOC. Photochemical oxidation is expressed using the reference unit, kg ethylene (C₂H₄) equivalent (kg C₂H₄ eq).
 - **Particulate matter potential.** This category is defined as suspended extremely small particles originated from anthropogenic processes such as combustion, resource extraction and other. Particulate pollution can be made up of a different number of components including acids, organic chemicals, metals, and soil or dust particles. It is measured in PM₁₀ equivalents, which are particles with a size of 10 µm.
- Agricultural land occupation potential.** This category is defined as impact of the land due to agriculture. It considers the relative species loss caused by a specific land use type (annual crops, permanent crops, mosaic agriculture, forestry, urban land, pasture). The species richness of the current, anthropogenic land use is compared with the natural reference, not accounting for any other anthropogenic land uses that may have been in place before the current land use. The potential damage is expressed in squared meter of land per year (m²a).
- **Water depletion potential.** The water related impacts are based on water consumption. Water consumption is the use of water in such a way that the water is evaporated, incorporated into products, transferred to other watersheds or disposed into the sea. Water

that has been consumed is thus not available anymore in the watershed of origin for humans nor for ecosystems. It is expressed in m³ of water consumed per m³ of water extracted. Water extraction is the withdrawal of water from surface water bodies or the abstraction of groundwater from aquifer. It is the total amount of water withdrawn, irrespective of return flows to the water bodies or water use efficiencies. Water consumption, on the other hand is the amount of water that the watershed of origin is losing.

3.3.4 Life cycle interpretation

The life cycle interpretation phase includes identification of the significant issues based on the results of the LCI and LCIA phases of the LCA; an evaluation that considers completeness, sensitivity, and consistency checks; conclusions, limitations, and recommendations (ISO 14044, 2020). This phase will be part of further work under WP 7 and the modelling of the DVCM, as mentioned in the theoretical framework, section 2.2 Streamlined life cycle assessment.

3.4 Streamlined Social Life Cycle Assessment

3.4.1 Basic methodological approach

The methodology of the sLCA was derived from the approach to an LCA, mainly from the ISO 14040. This means that the four steps of an LCA can also be used for an sLCA.

1. Goal and Scope: setting the goal and scope for the assessment,
2. Inventory: collecting data,
3. Impact assessment: assessing the risks and potential impacts with regard to products, services and organizations, and
4. Interpretation: interpreting results.

In this project ONEforest, the methodological approach from the UNEP Guidelines (UNEP, 2020) and the Handbook for Product Social Impact Assessment (Fontes, 2016) have been used.

Before starting with the setting of the goal and scope, a brief literature review was conducted to evaluate the availability of studies with a focus on sLCA in the forest and wood sector. Only a few relevant publications were found, mainly related to the choice of indicators (e.g. Siebert et al. 2018).

3.4.2 General assumptions

The study includes indicators and parameters relevant to the whole forest and wood value chain. Since there are specific differences between the stages in the forest wood value chain (e.g. risk of accidents are different for forest workers or office employees) the data will be collected as specific to the value chain stages as possible. This means that if figures or results are available for specific indicators then these will be used.

The statistical offices often include forestry in the sector "Agriculture, Forestry, and Fishery". This makes it rather difficult to evaluate how the figures or values are split between the three

sub-sectors. Therefore, the whole sector will be shown with the note of the integration of agricultural and fishery data.

The data, especially data regarding e.g. wages or accidents are average data in regard to the whole sector. This means that this can include an uneducated worker up to a highly skilled forest enterprise manager.

In the sLCA, which focusses often on not-quantifiable data, assumptions have to be made in regards to if an indicator shows a risk or a positive impact. This will be discussed in the following chapter “Life cycle interpretation and assessment”.

3.4.3 Definition of goal and scope

The goal of the sLCA is to provide an overview of social impacts in the forest wood sector. These social impacts can be risks or positive impacts for the human beings as employees, customers or any other stakeholder of the FWVC.

Since there are no publicly available data for all indicators specifically for the CSRs (except Estonia) available, the national borders will be the system boundaries. Therefore, the sLCA will be conducted for Estonia, Germany, Spain and Switzerland. The sLCA has a look at the whole forest wood value chain and will consider as much of the sector as possible. The focus and therefore the scope of the sLCA is not on a single product but on the whole sector in the specific country of a CSR.

Table 22: Overview Goal and Scope sLCA

Goal	The goal of the sLCA is to provide an overview of social impacts in the forest wood sector. These social impacts can be risks or positive impacts for the human beings as employees, customers or any other stakeholder of the FWVC.
Functional unit	No functional unit, specific units per indicator will be used
System boundary	National borders Focus on sector / FWVC
Assessment methodology	Scales-based approach
Indicators included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> payment according to basic wage [y/n] average wages and salaries per employee relative to the country average weekly hours of work per employee (contract) effective working hours per week per employee relative to country's average gender wage gap incidents/reported cases of discrimination accident rate at the workplace fatal accident rate at the workplace documented employment condition (e.g. contracts) number of persons employed in full-time-equivalents structure of ownership (small scale forest owners, small scale saw mills etc.) rate of land use change (e.g. from forest to infrastructure) contribution of the sector to environmental load actions to minimize the use of hazardous substances number of cases of disasters and pollution caused by the company activities presence of anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation presence of profit-sharing contract that is available and understood by all contract farmers that is impartial membership in an initiative that promotes social responsibility along the supply chain firm's code of ethics applied to all suppliers supplier's code of ethics applied policy/legislation available?

	the organization has pledged to comply with the global compact principles and has engaged itself to present yearly
	contribution of the sector to economic development
	investments in technology development/technology transfer
General assumptions	Indicators relevant for FWVC
	Average data include all workers of the specific FWVC stage / sector
Type and sources of data	Publicly available data from international and national organisations

3.4.4 Units and indicators

Deriving from different categories, the following table shows indicators which are used for the inventory analysis. The categories were chosen from the UNEP Guidelines (2020) and the indicators were adapted to fit the forest wood sector.

Table 23: Categories and Indicators of the sLCA

Categories	Indicators
Fair salary	payment according to basic wage [y/n] average wages and salaries per employee relative to the country average
Working hours	weekly hours of work per employee (contract) effective working hours per week per employee relative to country's average
Equal opportunities / discrimination	gender wage gap incidents/reported cases of discrimination
Health and safety	accident rate at the workplace fatal accident rate at the workplace
Employment relationship	documented employment condition (e.g. contracts) number of persons employed in full-time-equivalents
Smallholders including farmers	structure of ownership (small scale forest owners, small scale saw mills etc.)
Cultural heritage	rate of land use change (e.g. from forest to infrastructure)
Safe and healthy living conditions	contribution of the sector to environmental load actions to minimize the use of hazardous substances number of cases of disasters and pollution caused by the company activities
Fair competition	presence of anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation presence of profit-sharing contract that is available and understood by all contract farmers that is impartial
Promoting social responsibility	membership in an initiative that promotes social responsibility along the supply chain
Supplier relationships	firm's code of ethics applied to all suppliers supplier's code of ethics applied
End-of-life responsibility	policy/legislation available?
Public commitments to sustainability issues	the organization has pledged to comply with the global compact principles and has engaged itself to present yearly
Contribution to economic development	contribution of the sector to economic development
Technology development	investments in technology development/technology transfer

In comparison to the LCA standard, a common functional unit is difficult to agree on in sLCAs. Since social indicators are not always quantifiable, a functional unit can only be used for some indicators. Therefore, in this study each indicator received its own specific unit for calculation.

Table 24: Indicators and units of the sLCA

Indicators	Units
payment according to basic wage [y/n]	€/yr
average wages and salaries per employee relative to the country average	%
weekly hours of work per employee (contract)	hrs
effective working hours per week per employee relative to country's average	%
gender wage gap (salary difference)	%
incidents/reported cases of discrimination	number
accident rate at the workplace	number/yr
fatal accident rate at the workplace	number/yr
documented employment condition (e.g. contracts)	number
number of persons employed in full-time-equivalents	fte
structure of ownership (small scale forest owners, small scale saw mills etc.)	
contribution of the sector to environmental load	see LCA
actions to minimize the use of hazardous substances	text
number of cases of disasters and pollution caused by the company activities	number
presence of anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation	yes/no
presence of profit-sharing contract that is available and understood by all contract farmers that is impartial	yes/no
membership in an initiative that promotes social responsibility along the supply chain	yes/no + number/sector or ha/certification scheme
firm's code of ethics applied to all suppliers	yes/no
supplier's code of ethics applied	yes/no
the organization has pledged to comply with the global compact principles and has engaged itself to present yearly	yes/no
contribution of the sector to economic development	% of GDP
investments in technology development/technology transfer	% of turnover

3.4.5 Life cycle inventory analysis

Data was collected from openly available sources, such as databanks from international organisation, local or federal statistical offices and insurance companies.

International data sources are for example:

- FAO
- ILO
- OECD
- UNESCO
- Eurostat, etc.

National data sources are for example:

- Statistisches Bundesamt (Germany)
- Statistics Estonia (Estonia)
- Bundesamt für Statistik (Schweiz)
- Subdirección General de Estadística y Análisis Sociolaboral (Spain)

For the inventory analysis, always the newest data was collected with regard to the year of publication and the reference year. Since not all data was available for 2020 and 2021, some older data was taken into account, too.

Table 25: Indicators and reference year

Indicator	Reference Year
payment according to basic wage [y/n]	2021
average wages and salaries per employee relative to the country average	
weekly hours of work per employee (contract)	2018
effective working hours per week per employee relative to country's average	
gender wage gap	2021
incidents/reported cases of discrimination	
accident rate at the workplace	2020
fatal accident rate at the workplace	
documented employment condition (e.g. contracts)	2019
number of persons employed in full-time-equivalents	
structure of ownership (small scale forest owners, small scale saw mills etc.)	2019
contribution of the sector to environmental load	2020
actions to minimize the use of hazardous substances	
number of cases of disasters and pollution caused by the company activities	
presence of anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation	-
presence of profit-sharing contract that is available and understood by all contract farmers that is impartial	
membership in an initiative that promotes social responsibility along the supply chain	2022
contribution of the sector to economic development	2021
investments in technology development/technology transfer	2020

3.4.6 Life cycle interpretation and assessment

The weighing process for an interpretation of the results is very difficult in the context of social life cycle assessment. There are different approaches possible, one of which is the score per reference scale per social topic¹:

Figure 3: Example of score per reference scale per social topic¹

The score per references scale shows the best in class to worst in class. The difficulty is the comparison between different classes (here in ONEforest the comparison between different CSR). The classes are all relatively scored, which means that the best in class in one CSR could be the worst in class in another CSR.

The interpretation of the results should be therefore always done by the user in relation to their set goals or targets.

¹ Source of Figure 3: <https://www.social-value-initiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/20-01-Handbook2020.pdf>, page 12

Another possible reference scale is the weighting into poor and better social performance. This already includes an dimensionless application of relative social scores. The following figure shows an example of this assessment scale².

Fig. 2. The assessment scale from zero (i.e., relatively poor social performance) to ten (i.e., relatively better social performance) is applied to calculate dimensionless relative social scores from the organisations' indicator values and the performance reference points.

Figure 4: Assessment scale from zero to ten in relation to social performance²

The second assessment scale already needs high quality data to perform the weighting into poor and better social performance. But in comparison to the first mentioned weighting scale, the latter one is “more related to the product” (Siebert et al., 2018).

This performance of the weighting of the results will not be conducted within this deliverable. The data quality is not sufficient enough to do this assessment.

² Source of figure 4: A. Siebert, S. O'Keeffe, A. Bezama, W. Zeug, D. Thrän (2018): How not to compare apples and oranges: Generate context-specific performance reference points for a social life cycle assessment model, Journal of Cleaner Production, Volume 198, 2018, pp. 587-600.

4 Results

4.1 MFA

4.1.1 CSR 1 Estonia

MFA model of CSR 1 Estonia contains 116 equations and 255 variables which of 55 variables were unknown, six transfer coefficients (e.g. processing yields), and five subprocess variables. The degree of over-determination is 13, which means the model contains 13 more equations than unknown variables after transforming the system of equations. The quality of data reconciliation is at 0.81 proving that data reconciliation was necessary to solve the heterogenic data sets, confirming a low heterogeneous character of data, as the maximum value of data reconciliation is 1. However, the quality of data used was good enough to solve data contradictions resulting in 20 adjustments in variables (8%) (Table 26).

Table 26. Reconciled values with standard z-scores in comparison to given and by the MFA calculated values for CSR 1 Estonia.

Flow abbreviation	Flow name	standard scores z	input flow value (m ³ (f))	input standard uncertainty (m ³ (f))	output flow value calculated (m ³ (f))	output standard uncertainty calculated (m ³ (f))	variation
B TMP	bark from thermomechanical pulp	0.01	25,037	522	25,031	521	↓
FW HP	fuelwood for heat production	0.1	14,000	8,178	13,205	5,197	↓
HW FW POP	hardwood fuelwood for power production	0.08	11,200	6,524	11,706	5,140	↑
HW PW PB	hardwood pulpwood for particleboard production	0.08	16,349	4,472	16,006	3,001	↓
HW PW TMP	hardwood pulpwood for thermomechanical pulp process	0.16	391,204	8,155	389,903	5,564	↓
HW PW WPI	hardwood pulpwood for wood panel industry	0.08	16,349	4,472	16,006	3,001	↓
HW PW WRF	hardwood pulpwood from forest (FAO)	2.09	1,343,333	50,064	1,448,069	37,244	↑
HW PWE	hardwood pulpwood exported	2.31	1,174,920	55,292	1,047,168	37,309	↓
HW PWI	hardwood pulpwood imported	0.12	6,390	2,959	6,756	2,957	↑
OSB	osb produced	0.06	108,290	7,128	107,836	5,032	↓

PB	particleboard produced	0.06	30,339	8,298	29,822	4,723	
SW CWP	softwood wood pulp produced	0.02	142,859	2,221	142,816	1,680	
SW FW HP	softwood fuelwood for heat production	0.02	2,800	1,631	2,832	1,612	
SW PW KSP	softwood pulpwood for kraft (sulfate) process	0.02	163,829	2,547	163,785	1,684	
SW PW OSB	softwood pulpwood for osb production	0.06	124,186	8,174	123,665	5,771	
SW PW PB	softwood pulpwood for particleboard production	0.04	17,249	4,718	17,069	4,168	
SW PW WRF	softwood pulpwood from forest (FAO)	0.73	1,320,000	46,969	1,354,364	41,951	
SW PWE	softwood pulpwood exported	1.43	1,242,440	91,760	1,111,284	43,826	
SW PWI	softwood pulpwood imported	0.24	57,880	15,118	61,440	14,959	
TMP	(thermo) mechanical pulp produced	0.17	366,167	7,633	364,872	5,563	

The MFA of CSR 1 results in a high volume of exported pulpwood for both hardwood and softwood. In 2018, 1.45 Mio. m³(f) hardwood and 1.35 Mio m³(f) softwood pulpwood was removed from Estonian forests. However, 73% (1.05 Mio. m³(f)) of hardwood and 82% (1.11 Mio. m³(f)) of softwood pulpwood were exported as roundwood without contributing to the Estonian FWVC due to less or even missing pulpwood processing industries such as the panel or the pulp and biorefinery industry.

Furthermore, the MFA displays a flow with the value of 2.60 Mio. m³(f) composing mostly out of hardwood fuelwood and 0.52 Mio. m³(f) hardwood sawlogs, which is not directly allocable to the domestic consumption or to exports. May the volumes be used and were not recorded as products or they are exported without recording.

In 2018, Statistics Estonia (Statistics Estonia, 2022b) recorded 1.69 Mio. m³(f) softwood sawnwood produced. The MFA detected a higher softwood sawnwood production by 3.30 Mio. m³(f) which means a nearly two times higher production volume as recorded. Accordingly, statistics recorded a hardwood sawnwood production by 0.88 Mio. m³(f) and the MFA displayed 1.02 Mio. m³(f). One weak point seems to be the pellets producing industry. Based on Estonian company reports, a share of 66% by-products and 34% fuelwood is assumed. Whereas by-products are allocated with 95% to softwood and 5% to hardwood (following the share of produced sawnwood), and fuelwood is distributed with 20% to softwood and 80% to hardwood. Thereupon, one hypothesis could be that more fuelwood made from hardwood than from softwood by-products is processed to produce pellets. However, the advertised pellet plus certification seems to be contrarily to this hypothesis.

However, it is questionable to what extent this corresponds to reality. The high value is due to the high demand for sawmill by-products from the pellet production. Assuming that the input share distribution of the pellet production is correct and that the import figures for softwood sawmill by-products are correct, the high demand for sawmill by-products can only be met by a higher production of sawnwood with a resulting higher volume of sawmill by-products. The same applies to the hardwood sawnwood production.

Figure 5 to Figure 10 show the subordinate level and the subprocesses of the CSR 1 MFA model whereas the thickness of the arrows demonstrates to the quantities of wood.

Figure 5. MFA screenshot of the CSR 1 Estonia—subordinate level.

Figure 6. MFA screenshot of the CSR 1 Estonia—wood available in market.

Figure 7. MFA screenshot of the CSR 1 Estonia—wood panel industry.

Figure 8. MFA screenshot of the CSR 1 Estonia—pulp and biorefinery industry.

Figure 9. MFA screenshot of the CSR 1 Estonia—wood energy product industry.

Figure 10. MFA screenshot of the CSR 1 Estonia—energy production.

4.1.2 CSR 2 Grisons (CH)

The Grisons MFA model contains 46 equations and 166 variables which of 59 variables were unknown, two transfer coefficients (e.g. processing yields), and two subprocess variables. The degree of over-determination is 3, which means the model contains 3 more equations than unknown variables after transforming the system of equations. The quality of data reconciliation is at 0.71 proving that data reconciliation was necessary to solve the heterogenic data sets, confirming the heterogeneous character of data and the distinct need for adjustments, as the maximum value of data reconciliation is 1. However, the quality of data used was good enough to solve data contradictions resulting in 10 variable adjustments (6%), whereof nine variables have an z-score below 0.5 (Table 27).

Table 27. Reconciled values with standard z-scores in comparison to given and by the MFA calculated values for CSR 2 Grisons.

Flow abbreviation	Flow name	standard scores z	input flow value (m ³ (f))	input standard uncertainty y (m ³ (f))	output flow value calculated (m ³ (f))	output standard uncertainty	variation
HW PW WRPF	hardwood pulpwood from private-owned forests	0.01	150	38	150	37	
HW FW WRSF	hardwood fuelwood from state-owned forests	0.04	12,835	1,284	12,887	1,283	
HW PWE	hardwood pulpwood exported	0.04	161	130	167	99	
HW PW WRSF	hardwood pulpwood from state-owned forests	0.05	24	148	17	100	
SW PW WRPF	softwood pulpwood from private-owned forests	0.06	954	113	947	112	
SW FW WRSF	softwood fuelwood from state-owned forests	0.09	107,209	2,682	107,437	2,677	
SWSLVLR SF	softwood sawlogs/veneer logs from state-owned forests	0.24	258,845	7,568	260,662	7,463	
SW PWE	softwood pulpwood exported	0.35	4,141	670	4,372	513	
SW PW WRSF	softwood pulpwood from state-owned forests	0.38	3,725	788	3,425	515	
WRSF	wood removals from state-owned forests	1.42	448,505	44,851	384,690	8,017	

Main findings of the MFA are the high volume of softwood sawlogs/veneer logs 211'144.99 +/- 11.05 m³(f) which are obviously exported with approx. 92% (194'302.72 +/- 11.05 m³(f)). The remaining approx. 17'000 m³(f) softwood sawlogs/veneer logs and 719.31 +/- 148 m³(f) hardwood sawlogs/veneer logs seemed to be used for energy production. Compared to the domestic processing of softwood sawlogs/veneer logs with 25'850 +/- 2.59 the export is remarkable. These results are largely in line with the Wood Flow Analysis of Grisons conducted by (Bartlome and Vlaskou Badra, 2021).

Figure 11 and the following show the subordinate level of the CSR2 MFA, whereas the thickness of the arrows demonstrates to the quantities of wood.

Figure 11. MFA screenshot of the CSR 2 Grisons—subordinate level.

Figure 12. MFA screenshot of the CSR 2 Grisons—wood available in market.

Figure 13. MFA screenshot of the CSR 2 Grisons—energy production.

4.1.3 CSR3 Catalonia (ES)

MFA model of CSR 3 Catalonia contains 106 equations and 245 variables which of 35 variables were unknown, 4 transfer coefficients (e.g. processing yields), and 3 subprocess variables. The degree of over-determination is 4, which means the model contains 4 more equations than unknown variables after transforming the system of equations. The quality of data reconciliation is at 0.67 proving that data reconciliation was necessary to solve the heterogenic data sets, confirming a heterogeneous character of data, as the maximum value of data reconciliation is 2. However, the quality of data used is good enough to solve data contradictions resulting in 19 adjustments in variables (8%) (Table 28

Table 27).

Table 28. Reconciled values with standard z-scores in comparison to given and by the MFA calculated values for CSR 3 Catalonia.

Flow abbreviation	Flow name	standard scores z	input flow value (m ³ (f))	input standard uncertainty (m ³ (f))	output flow value calculated (m ³ (f))	output standard uncertainty	variation
SW FW UWR	softwood fuelwood from unrecorded wood removals	2.02	33,328	11,418	10,276	7,259	
SW FW WRPF	softwood fuelwood from private-owned forests	1.56	55,700	8,799	42,012	7,073	
SW FW EI	softwood fuelwood for energy industry	0.59	52,132	3,312	54,071	3,228	
SWSLVLW RPF	softwood sawlogs/veneer logs from private-owned forests	0.31	377,160	22,094	370,211	15,724	
SW BP PEP	softwood by-products for pellets production	0.29	153,454	14,568	157,688	5,659	
PE EI	pellets for energy industry	0.13	130,338	12,495	131,937	10,087	
PEI	pellets imported	0.12	27,606	11,687	26,207	9,745	
PEE	pellets exported	0.11	63,621	10,921	64,842	9,356	
SW BP PS	softwood by-products from poles and stakes industry	0.09	41,567	6,827	42,158	5,372	
SWSLVLW RSF	softwood sawlogs/veneer logs from state-owned forests	0.08	71,506	5,880	71,014	5,766	
SW SLVLI	softwood sawlogs/veneer logs imported	0.07	48,972	4,897	48,631	4,837	
SW BP E	softwood by-products exported	0.05	17,300	1,730	17,390	1,716	
SW BP SI	softwood by-products from sawmill industry	0.05	131,479	6,282	131,786	5,354	
SW FWI	softwood fuelwood imported	0.04	2,041	204	2,034	204	
SW FW WRSF	softwood fuelwood from state-owned forests	0.03	175	191	169	191	
SW BP I	softwood by-products imported	0.02	6,243	624	6,231	624	

SW SLVLE	softwood sawlogs/veneer logs exported	0.02	11,426	1,143	11,445	1,142	
SW BP EI	softwood by-products for energy industry	0.02	5,089	509	5,097	509	
HW BP PEP	hardwood by-products for pellets production	0.01	12,899	1,225	12,884	1,223	

The flows with higher variability in Catalonia correspond mainly to softwood fuelwood, from unrecorded wood removals, and from private-owned forests supposed to use for energy production. The fuelwood from unrecorded wood removals was estimated based on the wood chips reported by OFC (OFC, 2021). They estimated the quantity integrating three different sources, the biomass boiler observatory, the biomass observatory from the Spanish Association for Energy Recovery from Biomass, the Diputació de Barcelona (a local government institution). The aggregated data include quantity of wood chips used in installations of boilers, burners, stoves but does not include fireplaces and firewood inserts. The data retrieved does not specified if the wood chips are from the forest or from by-products. To estimate the quantity of forest wood chips consumed to produce energy it was needed to estimate the share between wood chips as by-products and forest wood chips. The fuelwood flows were estimated summing the amounts of firewood reported by Idescat and the estimated forest wood chips (Idescat, 2021, 2019; OFC, 2021). The differences of softwood fuelwood from unrecorded wood removals and for energy industry can be caused by the estimation of the apparent consumption from different sources (official and non-official), which means that the volumes of fuelwood used for energy production is not reported centralized and it is difficult to calculate precisely the volumes consumed for energy production.

The CSR 3 MFA results in a higher volume of imported flows, such as softwood fuelwood for energy industry, pellets for energy industry, pellets imported, softwood sawlogs/veneer logs imported, softwood by-products from sawmill industry, softwood fuelwood imported, softwood by-products imported and softwood by-products for energy industry. This is due to the foreign trade data reported by Idescat only considers import and export data between Catalonia and other countries, neglecting the trade amounts between Catalonia and other Spanish states.

Because of the foreign trade data explained before, the flows identified as softwood and hardwood pulpwood unknown sink where placed as input flows for roundwood and fuelwood exported instead of being inputs for the energy industry. As mentioned in the method and material subsection 3.2.5 CSR 3 Catalonia, there is not internal consumption of pulpwood, therefore the pulpwood flows correspond to pulpwood exported from Catalonia to other Spanish States. In addition, it was identified that there was an input flow of hardwood sawlogs/veneer logs from unrecorded wood removals. This can be also be assumed as an imported flow from other Spanish States to Catalonia.

For the energy industry, there is a high uncertainty for input volume of by-products used to produce energy. There was no information available of the volume of by-products used to produce energy. The volumes were estimated using the share of by-products imported used for energy production retrieved from the National Wood Balance (Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, 2020).

From Figure 14 to Figure 17, the graphical result for the CSR3 MFA model are shown. The thickness of the arrows illustrates the quantities of wood.

Figure 14. MFA screenshot of the CSR 3 Catalonia—subordinate level.

Figure 15. MFA screenshot of the CSR 3 Catalonia—wood available in market.

Figure 16. MFA screenshot of the CSR 3 Catalonia—wood energy product industry.

Figure 17. MFA screenshot of the CSR 3 Catalonia—energy production.

4.1.4 CSR4 Hesse and Thuringia (DE)

MFA model of CSR 4 Hesse and Thuringia contains 122 equations and 283 variables which of 67 variables were unknown, four transfer coefficients (e.g. processing yields), and five sub-process variables. The degree of over-determination is 3, which means the model contains 3 more equations than unknown variables after transforming the system of equations. The quality of data reconciliation is at 0.86 proving that data reconciliation was necessary to solve the heterogenic data sets, confirming the heterogeneous character of data, as the maximum value of data reconciliation is one. However, the quality of data used was good enough to solve data contradictions resulting in 9 adjustments in variables (3%) (Table 29).

Table 29. Reconciled values with standard z-scores in comparison to given and by the MFA calculated values for CSR 4 Germany.

Flow abbreviation	Flow name	standard scores z	input flow value (m³(f))	input standard uncertainty (m³(f))	output flow value calculated (m³(f))	output standard uncertainty calculated (m³(f))	variation

HW PW PB	hardwood pulpwood for particleboard production	0.04	60,351	6,035	60,589	5,990	
PB	particleboard produced	0.29	437,500	43,750	425,004	20,174	
PCW PB	post-consumer wood for particleboard production	0.07	103,645	10,054	104,305	9,843	
SW B KSP	softwood bark from kraft (sulfate) process	0.06	49,985	4,998	49,694	4,991	
SW BP KSP	softwood by-products for kraft (sulfate) process	0.34	289,593	28,959	299,377	27,505	
SW BP PB	softwood by-products for particleboard production	0.12	178,488	17,849	180,568	16,638	
SW CWP	softwood wood pulp produced	0.89	766,800	76,680	698,200	42,954	
SW PW KSP	softwood pulpwood for kraft (sulfate) process	0.50	427,222	42,722	448,516	37,900	
SW PW PB	softwood pulpwood for particleboard production	0.05	76,892	7,689	77,278	7,595	

Finally, the MFA proved that the data available on a Federal State level of Germany is heterogeneous. Approx. 5.6 Mio. m³ (f) softwood sawlogs/veneer logs were processed within the CSR and they seemed to be imported from other German Federal States. This could be reasonable since some big sawmills producing more than 0.5 Mio. m³ (f) softwood sawnwood are located close to the boarder within the CSR.

0.8 Mio. m³(f) pulpwood (0.4 Mio. m³ (f) hardwood, 0.4 Mio. m³ (f)) and mainly hardwood fuelwood (0.4 Mio. m³ (f)) is exported from the CSR. One reason of the high export volume of pulpwood might be that pulp mills located near the CSR border. However, this could not be proved due to missing data on the trade relationships between the Federal States.

In line with other studies (Auer and Rauch, 2021a; Bösch et al., 2015), this MFA detected missing and highly aggregated data in the energy production. The energy production almost is not traceable on a national level and it is getting even worse on a Federal State level. A high volume of bark should be used in the energy production even if the MFA results show that 1.0 Mio. m³ (f) bark are exported. Additionally, it was not possible to connect the hardwood fuelwood and the pulpwood flows in a reliable manner within the system boundaries due to missing information. Thus, 0.4 Mio. m³ (f) hardwood fuelwood, 0.3 Mio. m³ (f) softwood, and 0.3 Mio m³ (f) hardwood pulpwood are allocated to an unknown consumption within or outside the CSR.

Figure 18 to Figure 23 show the graphical result for the CSR 4 MFA model and sub-processes, whereas the thickness of the arrows demonstrates the quantities of wood.

Figure 18. MFA screenshot of the CSR 4 Hesse/Thuringia—subordinate level.

Figure 19. MFA screenshot of the CSR 4 Hesse/Thuringia—wood available in market.

Figure 20. MFA screenshot of the CSR 4 Hesse/Thuringia —wood panel industry.

Figure 21. MFA screenshot of the CSR 4 Hesse/Thuringia—pulp and biorefinery industry.

Figure 22. MFA screenshot of the CSR 4 Hesse/Thuringia—wood energy product industry.

Figure 23. MFA screenshot of the CSR 4 Hesse/Thuringia—energy production.

4.2 LCA

Table 31 shows the results of environmental impact categories of the semi-finished products produced in the CSRs along FWVC. The interpretation of this results, along with comparison between environmental impact categories among CSRs and further discussions, it will be published in scientific articles.

Table 30. Results of the environmental impact categories for each semi-finished product produced in each CSR.

Impact assessment method			CML-IA baseline											ei - ReCiPe Midpoint (H)		
Environmental impact category			ADP	ADPF	AP	EP	FAETP	GWP	HTP	MAEP	ODP	POP	TETP	PMFP	ALOP	WDP
CSR	Industry	FU	[kg Sb eq]	[MJ]	[kg SO2 eq]	[kg PO4 eq]	[kg 1,4-DB eq]	[kg CO2 eq]	[kg 1,4-DB eq]	[kg 1,4-DB eq]	[kg CFC-11 eq]	[kg C2H4 eq]	[kg 1,4-DB eq]	[kg PM10 eq]	[m2a]	[m3]
Sawmill, Poles and Stakes, Veneer Industry																
1	sawmilling softwood	1 m ³	0.00	946.54	0.54	0.13	13.08	70.72	28.46	22,982.50	0.00	0.06	0.35	0.29664	2284.01607	0.22658
	sawmilling hardwood	1 m ³	0.00	1,243.70	0.71	0.18	18.15	92.90	38.57	31,366.10	0.00	0.09	0.52	0.41224	2802.98521	0.3323
	poles and stakes softwood	1 m ³	0.00	3,933.20	1.13	0.47	14,317.10	406.16	246.79	21,2276.00	0.00	0.13	0.45	0.64285	1934.20485	0.84367
	veneer and plywood production softwood	1 m ³	0.00	11,630.50	5.92	1.12	214.25	712.87	409.17	394,315.00	0.00	0.42	1.88	2.26914	3199.08821	1.52373
	veneer and plywood production hardwood	1 m ³	0.00	11,685.70	5.93	1.14	216.79	717.07	411.40	397,624.00	0.00	0.45	2.04	2.27547	3699.58637	1.43051
2	sawmilling softwood	1 m ³	0.00	399.42	0.23	0.09	8.28	29.50	15.36	13,302.80	0.00	0.05	0.32	0.20248	2279.38757	0.19773
	sawmilling hardwood	1 m ³	0.00	513.37	0.31	0.13	11.70	38.12	21.00	18,374.70	0.00	0.08	0.47	0.28702	2796.99984	0.29383
3	sawmilling softwood	1 m ³	0.00014	616.42128	0.33993	0.11465	13.61829	46.50569	21.458	3.36E+04	6.29E-06	5.23E-02	0.33661	0.34154	2797.50941	0.34451
	sawmilling hardwood	1 m ³	0.0002	811.05591	0.45984	0.16161	18.76906	61.21716	2.94E+01	4.49E+04	8.27E-06	8.11E-02	0.5009	0.24264	2279.77562	0.23629
	poles and stakes softwood	1 m ³	0.00157	3402.0671	0.8262	0.45059	1.43E+04	366.95797	235.75777	2.31E+05	2.17E-05	0.09622	0.34736	0.56481	2537.81004	0.80516
	poles and stakes hardwood	1 m ³	0.00146	2916.565	0.64149	0.39483	1.43E+04	331.34218	221.10685	2.08E+05	1.67E-05	0.07746	0.18405	0.48117	15.7191	0.67712
Impact assessment method			CML-IA baseline											ei - ReCiPe Midpoint (H)		
Environmental impact category			ADP	ADPF	AP	EP	FAETP	GWP	HTP	MAEP	ODP	POP	TETP	PMFP	ALOP	WDP
CSR	Industry	FU	[kg Sb eq]	[MJ]	[kg SO2 eq]	[kg PO4 eq]	[kg 1,4-DB eq]	[kg CO2 eq]	[kg 1,4-DB eq]	[kg 1,4-DB eq]	[kg CFC-11 eq]	[kg C2H4 eq]	[kg 1,4-DB eq]	[kg PM10 eq]	[m2a]	[m3]

Sawmill, Poles and Stakes, Veneer Industry																
4	sawmilling softwood	1 m ³	0.00015	732.87948	0.29536	0.20835	28.38904	58.59467	28.977	6.01E+04	6.50E-06	5.12E-02	0.34955	0.23043	2279.8926	0.29062
	sawmilling hardwood	1 m ³	0.00022	971.61948	0.40522	0.2832	37.94025	77.4942	39.33344	7.93E+04	8.68E-06	7.98E-02	5.19E-01	0.32735	2797.66549	0.41516
	veneer and plywood production hardwood	1 m ³	0.00471	7792.3623	3.55645	1.02577	226.01879	429.72786	330.25924	5.35E+05	5.38E-05	0.35325	1.88852	1.43012	3647.9326	2.22558
Wood-based panel industry																
1	particle board production	1 m ³	0.004	8621.55	2.72	0.64	155.34	494.96	306.21	280976.00	8.04E-05	0.22	1.01	1.16259	1241.18541	1.04889
	OSB production		0.002	4953.24	2.18	0.56	91.35	276.19	186.14	175918.00	4.90E-05	0.22	0.90	0.88443	2979.19132	0.90957
	MDF, HDF, LDF, and other fiberboards production	1 m ³	0.01	10941.78	4.02	0.93	231.56	650.62	411.97	440012.09	8.09E-05	0.34	1.36	1.58	1371.00	1.99
4	particle board production	1 m ³	0.004	8198.33	2.16	0.85	195.18	471.47	310.65	376539.00	6.95E-05	0.20	0.98	1.01491	739.87589	1.20473

Impact assessment method			CML-IA baseline											ei - ReCiPe Midpoint (H)		
Environmental impact category			ADP	ADPF	AP	EP	FAETP	GWP	HTP	MAEP	ODP	POP	TETP	PMFP	ALOP	WDP
CSR	Industry	FU	[kg Sb eq]	[MJ]	[kg SO2 eq]	[kg PO4 eq]	[kg 1,4-DB eq]	[kg CO2 eq]	[kg 1,4-DB eq]	[kg 1,4-DB eq]	[kg CFC-11 eq]	[kg C2H4 eq]	[kg 1,4-DB eq]	[kg PM10 eq]	[m2a]	[m3]
Pulp and paper industry																

1	pulp production (kraft or sulfate process)	1 kg	1.74E-06	4.04219	0.0025	0.00114	0.16185	0.31621	0.17128	534.68194	5.26E-08	0.00014	0.00089	0.00124	6.73272	0.00092
	thermo mechanical pulp process	1 kg	4.967E-06	29.78981	0.01794	0.0029	0.31645	2.17986	0.84	362.22529	3.967E-07	0.00074	0.00414	0.00539	2.87054	0.00397
4	pulp production (kraft or sulfate process)	1 kg	1.81E-06	3.91986	0.00227	0.00128	0.18057	0.31019	0.17469	570.91781	5.01E-08	0.00025	0.00146	0.00117	5.33173	0.00133
Wood energy product industry																
1	pellet production Industrial Pellets	1 kg	2.72E-05	2.01E+02	4.60E-02	1.06E-02	2.51E+00	1.44E+01	3.26E+00	4.24E+03	2.39E-06	2.98E-03	9.15E-03	1.97E-02	1.64E+00	7.13E-03
	pellet production Norm Pellets	1 kg	5.48E-07	4.59E+00	2.53E-03	7.37E-04	1.38E-01	4.74E-01	1.44E-01	4.28E+02	1.78E-08	8.35E-04	6.48E-04	7.33E-04	9.73E-01	8.37E-04
	briquette production	1 kg	4.98E-06	2.58E+01	7.78E-03	2.54E-03	4.44E-01	2.00E+00	5.63E-01	9.04E+02	2.84E-07	1.08E-03	1.67E-03	3.13E-03	1.67E+00	1.57E-03
	charcoal production	1 kg	3.82E-07	2.32E+00	9.04E-04	3.78E-04	5.62E-02	1.33E+00	6.52E-02	1.36E+02	1.95E-08	8.87E-03	1.12E-03	8.39E-04	6.25E+00	8.55E-04
3	pellet production	1 kg	5.44E-07	4.58E+00	2.53E-03	7.36E-04	1.38E-01	4.73E-01	1.44E-01	4.27E+02	1.76E-08	8.35E-04	6.46E-04	7.31E-04	9.73E-01	8.36E-04
4	pellet production	1 kg	5.50E-07	4.60E+00	2.54E-03	7.38E-04	1.38E-01	4.74E-01	1.45E-01	4.28E+02	1.79E-08	8.35E-04	6.49E-04	7.35E-04	9.73E-01	8.37E-04

4.3 sLCA

The data provided are the results of a research in various databases, statistical material and literature. The results stated here are an overview of what is possible to integrate in the social life cycle assessment. Nevertheless, more and different data will be used in WP7 for the dynamic value chain model.

a) Membership in an initiative that promotes social responsibility along the supply chain³

Table 32: Membership FSC and PEFC

Initiatives	Unit	Estonia	Switzerland	Germany	Spain
FSC	FM certified area in ha	1.240.656	554.261	1.439.832	495.429
PEFC	FM certified area in ha	1.326.220	222.551	8.753.895	2.567.976
FSC	National coverage %	50,9%	43,6%	12,6%	2,7%
PEFC	National coverage %	54,4%	17,5%	76,7%	13,8%
FSC	No. CoC certificates	307	420	2.259	1.467
PEFC	No. CoC certificates	102	74	1.729	1.077
Double certified	FSC+PEFC area in ha	1.063.407	208.949	895.682	131.828

b) Policy Coherence

In ONEforest, the D6.1 Policy Analysis focussed on the legislation in the CSRs. For this policy analysis, forest, climate, biodiversity, bioeconomy and energy policies were evaluated. The coherence was rather high in most cases for the forest, climate and often biodiversity policies. Whereas the energy and bioeconomy level of coherence was rather low.

Table 33: D6.1, Policy coherence

Catalonia (ES)*	Estonia*	Grisons (CH)*	Hesse/Thuringia (DE)*
High within forest policy and climate policy, as well as biodiversity – in forest-related issues.	High across levels in forest policy and climate policy.	High across levels in climate policy and forest policy. Also high between biodiversity and forest policy.	Relatively high across levels in forest and climate policy.
Low across levels in energy and bioeconomy.	Low across levels in energy, bioeconomy, and biodiversity policies.	Low across levels in biodiversity and energy.	Low across levels in biodiversity and energy policy.

³ Source: <https://fsc.org/en/facts-figures>, <https://pefc.org/discover-pefc/facts-and-figures> and <https://cdn.pefc.org/pefc.org/media/2019-04/baecf2a2-144e-4c47-a24b-7a5df7ba2a24/bc3a2d7d-78d4-5863-b11c-d363da8ec380.pdf>

c) Share of GDP in the countries of the CSR⁴

Table 34: Share of GDP

Share of GDP	Unit	EU	Estonia	Switzerland	Spain	Germany
Agriculture, forestry, and fishing, value added (current US\$)	mio. US\$/year	278151,68	777,23	5069,01	38882,59	33796,80
Agriculture, forestry, and fishing, value added (% of GDP)	%	1,60%	2,10%	0,60%	2,70%	0,80%

d) Investment in R&D (all sectors) in the countries of the CSR⁵

Table 35: Investment in R&D (all sectors) in the countries of the CSR

Investment in R&D	Unit	EU	Estonia	Switzerland	Spain	Germany
Investment in R&D total	mio. €/year	311.149	481	22.900	15.768	105.885
R&D expenditure percentage of GDP	%	2,30%	1,80%	3,15%	1,40%	3,10%

e) Gender pay gap (all sectors) in the countries of the CSR⁶

Table 36: Gender pay gap (all sectors) in the countries of the CSR

	Unit	Estonia	Switzerland	Spain	Germany
Gender pay gap	%	20,5%	17,7%	8,9%	17,6%

⁴ Source: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NV.AGR.TOTL.CD> and <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NV.AGR.TOTL.ZS>

⁵ Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/de/web/products-eurostat-news/-/ddn-20211129-2> and https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/rd_e_gerdtot/default/table?lang=de and <https://www.swissinfo.ch/eng/sci-tech/swiss-spend-almost-chf23-billion-on-research/46654784#:~:text=Switzerland%20spent%20CHF22.,the%20OECD%20average%20of%20.38%25.>

⁶ Source: Eurostat, Gender pay gap in unadjusted form [SDG_05_20]

5 Discussion of results and outlook of sLCA

The data is the basis for comprehensive assessments and analyses. Conducting the social life cycle assessment within this project, many difficulties were faced:

- a) Data was not available on the area level of the case study region, but only on national level. While this is not the case for CSR 1 (= national level of Estonia), the CSR 2, 3 and 4 are only regional levels or federal state levels where the statistical data availability is rather scarce for social indicators.
- b) Data was not available for the different sectors forestry, sawmills, panel industry, bioenergy etc. Often data is only aggregated in databases into “agriculture, fishery and forestry” or “manufacturing industry”. This makes it difficult to conduct a weighting for the data since it includes factors which are not considered within ONEforest.
- c) The data bases or sources for the different CSR have various different baselines, units and collection methods. This makes it very difficult to compare data between the different CSR and therefore also use a weighting system.
- d) Many factors are difficult to quantify, like factors regarding heritage, supplier relationships etc. For a weighting and assessment the quantification or at least the qualitative interpretation is needed.

Because of these above mentioned difficulties, the performance of the weighting of the results was not conducted within the time frame of this deliverable. The social factors will be part of the dynamic value chain model, though, and therefore the key factors and key impacts will be shown, which influence the social life cycle of the forest and wood products and value chains.

6 Preliminary results and outlook regarding MFA and LCA

The aim of this report is to model the FWVC through MFA and to assess environmental impacts of the semi-finished wood products included in the FWVC in each CSRs by performing a streamlined LCA. The MFA results are used to systematically collect sources and utilization of wood in the different CSRs. The results identified possible inaccuracies by data reconciliation as well as heterogenous characters of the data. The wood flows are evaluated from wood removals at the forest to volume semi-finished products processed in different industries, complemented by trade data of imports and exports flows. To do this, a general MFA model is created and adapted to the wood industry available in each CSR, this allowed to identify which semi-finished products are produced in each CSR. The relevance of MFA is to reconcile heterogeneous data aiming to provide one consistent dataset per CSR.

The available data and its quality are related to the spatial boundaries of the specific CSRs. For instance, data for Cantons or Federal States is difficult to gather since official statistics cannot provide data due to confidentiality issues. If the region is on a more subordinate level, e.g. Estonia as whole country hosts more companies producing same products, thus, less data must be kept confidential due to business issues. Therefore, one main finding is, that it is not possible to detect unrecorded fellings or unrecorded processing on a regional level specifically and reliable due to lack of data as (Auer and Rauch, 2021a) (2021a) proofed it for Germany.

After identifying the semi-finished products along the FWVC in each CSR, an LCA was conducted to assess the ecological effects along the FWVC. This report presents the result of the several environmental impact categories that shows the performance of wood semi-finished products for each CSR. Due to the methodology applied the differences in the results depend primarily on the regional background system. This includes the transport of wood (different regional distances) and the production of electricity (specific grid mixes for each country, where the respective CSR is located).

The obtained interim results of MFA and LCA are applied for modelling the DVCM and provide the basis for further analyses within the DVCM. The MFA and LCA presented results will be used as a baseline to develop the different future scenarios within the FWVC of the CSRs. This makes it possible to compare to the actual wood flows and the ecological impacts with future wood flows and ecological impacts. Thereupon, quantified recommendations for actions will be derived to ensure sustainable wood flows in the four CRS in the future.

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Appendix A: Foreground and background system per industry

LCA Modelling Approach: example kiln-dried sawwood (softwood and hardwood)
System boundary: cradle-to-gate (semi-finished products) *

* not considered: maintenance of machinery, construction of buildings and roads
*** differentiation between softwood and hardwood in harvesting/storage

Figure A. 2. Foreground and background system of hardwood/softwood sawwood production.

LCA Modelling Approach: example kiln-dried sawwood
System boundary: cradle-to-gate (semi-finished products) *

* not considered: maintenance of machinery, construction of buildings and roads
*** differentiation between softwood and hardwood in harvesting/storage needed in LCA

Figure A. 3. Foreground and background system of hardwood/softwood veneer and plywood production.

LCA Modelling Approach: poles and stakes production

System boundary: cradle-to-gate (semi-finished products) *

* not considered: maintenance of machinery, construction of buildings and roads
 *** differentiation between softwood and hardwood in harvesting/storage

Figure A. 4. Foreground and background system of hardwood/softwood poles and stakes production.

LCA Modelling Approach: example kraft pulp production out of the kraft process

System boundary: cradle-to-gate (semi-finished products) *

* not considered: maintenance of machinery, construction of buildings and roads
 *** differentiation between softwood and hardwood in harvesting/storage needed in LCA? How to deal with the sawing processes?

Figure A. 5. Foreground and background system of pulp production (kraft or sulfate process).

LCA Modelling Approach: Thermo mechanical pulp production

System boundary: cradle-to-gate (semi-finished products) *

Figure A. 6. Foreground and background system of thermo mechanical pulp production.

LCA Modelling Approach: example raw particleboard

System boundary: cradle-to-gate (semi-finished products) *

Figure A. 7. Foreground and background system of raw particleboard production.

LCA Modelling Approach: example OSB

System boundary: cradle-to-gate (semi-finished products) *

* not considered: maintenance of machinery, construction of buildings and roads

Figure A. 8. Foreground and background system of OSB production.

LCA Modelling Approach: MDF production

System boundary: MDF production (cradle-to-gate (semi-finished products)) *

* not considered: maintenance of machinery, construction of buildings and roads

Figure A. 9. Foreground and background system of MDF production.

System boundary: cradle-to-gate (semi-finished products) *

Figure A. 10. Foreground and background system of pellets production.

System boundary: cradle-to-gate (semi-finished products) *

Figure A. 11. Foreground and background system of briquettes production.

System boundary: cradle-to-gate (semi-finished products) *

Figure A. 12. Foreground and background system of charcoal production.

ONEforest

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